

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC

D3: Report on the expected energy savings potential in the EU area and projected mitigation of the heat-island effect in urban areas for different types of PRC materials taking into account thermal modelling and the associated tolerances of each material

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Glossary

AC	air conditioning
PRC	passive radiative cooling
PDRC	passive daytime radiative cooling
DRC	daytime radiative cooling
SS	spectral selective (PRC materials)
BB	broadband (PRC materials)
EMS	Energy Management System
MFB	Multifamily building
SFH	Single-family house
DH	Detached house
CDD	cooling degree days
PWV	precipitable water vapor

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1 Introduction

The aim of Task 2.3 in PaRaMeTriC was to quantify potential energy savings and potential reductions of heat-island effects in urban environments if passive cooling systems are used at large scale. The potential impact in terms of heat-island effect had to be modeled and quantified for typical types of urban areas and different geographic regions.

Within this framework, the Energy Department at Politecnico di Torino (POLITO) modelled a single-family two floors residential building corresponding, in terms of thermal performance, to construction practices for buildings erected between 1991 and 2005. The two floors are air-conditioned using a heat pump and the two cases with and without assistance of passive radiative cooling (PRC) panels to help overcool the refrigerant gas after the condenser were studied. Energy consumption was calculated for four locations of the building, for five types of PRC materials and using meteorological data sourced from the ERA5 Reanalysis dataset for the year 2023. Relative cooling energy savings obtained by adding PDRC panels to the air-cooling system of the building are about 6% to 10%. The spectral shape of the infrared emissivity curve of the PDRC panels has an effect on the efficiency of the global air-cooling system. The configuration of such a system must be optimized (areas of the PRC panels, flows of heat transfer fluid) to get a good performance.

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Physics Department (NKUA) modelled potential energy savings when PRC systems are used purely passively in the building envelope. Four different types of buildings were modelled; each one located in a specific city in the south of Europe. Energy consumption modelling was done versus time using climatic data from the nearest meteorological station of each location. NKUA studied also the impact of the use of passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials at large scale in urban areas in terms of the reduction of overheating at the ground level (air temperature). The study was carried on for two locations in Greece: Heraklion (Crete) and Neos Kosmos (Athens). The model was validated by comparison to experimental climatic data. The study showed that the use of PRC yields strong reductions of cooling needs for the detached single or two-story houses studied with relative reductions of primary cooling energy from -23.8% to -75.2%. The reduction is particularly high when roofs are not thermally insulated. For the annual primary energy consumption (cooling and heating), the energy gains throughout the year are from -5.4 % to +7.3 %; the gains during the cooling season are cancelled out by the reduction of solar energy gains during the heating season. The results confirm that PDRC materials used purely passively are effective in hot and dry climates for reducing cooling energy and thus cooling power and for maintaining acceptable temperatures in building poorly thermal insulated.

Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja - Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (IETC – CSIC) with the active participation of POLITO and CNR-INO modeled dynamically their experimental set-up with two cells used to test Hydronic cooling system and validate the model by comparison with experimental results. A Hydronic cooling system is a system with water circulation, passive cooling panels and ceiling-mounted radiant capacitive modules containing water in the building. The model was used for optimization of the configuration of the PRC system (area of the cooling panels and flow in the panels). Applications of the model have then been made for the case of a virtual modern two-story single-family residential building with a habitable area of 120m² along four months in summer (June to September). Three different PRC coatings with different spectral emissivity curves plus a black paint and three different implementations of the PRC system in the building were tested with the model for two locations in EU (Madrid and Rome). The indoor temperature, a comfort index specifically defined, and the energy removed from the building were calculated. The study showed that a based hydronic cooling system with panels coated with a passive radiative cooling material allows the increase of the energy removed from the building by 6% to 10 % comparatively to only nighttime cooling. The temperature inside the building can be maintained within comfortable range for more than 90% of the time in summer with an acceptable footprint of the cooling system. The seasonal coefficient of performance of the DRC-based hydronic system can be approximately 40 times higher than typical values reported for conventional air-conditioning systems. The findings underscore the potential of Hydronic cooling systems assisted with cooling panels coated with DRC materials to enable energy-efficient and almost completely passive cooling systems for buildings.

Forschungsinstitut für Wärmeschutz e.V. München (FIW München) estimated the potential of the passive radiative cooling technology on the reduction of energy demand for cooling German residential buildings within the next 30 years by comparison to classical cooling techniques. FIW collected climatic data (cloudiness, relative humidity, temperature) and found that in summer, the proportion of hours when atmosphere is

transparent enough in the spectral range 8 to 13 μm and when passive radiative cooling effect can be exploited is limited from 5 % to 15%. For residential buildings, around 10% to 15% fall into the top efficiency classes (A+, A, or B), whereas a significant share (often more than 50% in regional samples) is classified in the lowest categories (F to H). Two complementary approaches were applied to estimate future cooling demand. First, a linear projection based on historical energy consumption and mean annual temperatures indicates that total cooling demand could reach 18.5 TWh by 2050, representing a 70 % increase relative to 2020. Second, a household-based projection calculates residential demand bottom-up from household numbers and typical AC unit consumption, while non-residential demand is derived top-down from total energy consumption. Two scenarios were analyzed: Case A, with moderate AC penetration (4 % in 2024 rising to 14 % in 2050) and a 25 % climate-driven demand increase, resulting in total cooling demand rising from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 13.6 TWh in 2050. whereas Case B adopts the total energy consumption from the linear projection (18.5 TWh in 2050) and higher AC penetration (8 % in 2024 to 20 % in 2050). Potential energy and CO₂ savings from PDRC technologies, including envelope-integrated and device-based applications, are estimated as a combined range. Savings in Case A are 110 – 545 GWh and 6100 – 244000 t CO₂, increasing proportionally in Case B to 11 – 741 GWh and 6100–244000 t CO₂. These results demonstrate that PDRC technologies can reduce energy consumption and emissions, particularly under high-demand scenarios.

Center for Applied Energy Research (CAE) studied the impact of using PRC techniques at large scale on the envelope of buildings by thermal modelling an urban canyon with the roofs and the walls of the buildings covered with usual materials or PRC material. Results show that the roofs temperatures can be reduced significantly (20 to 25 °C). With PRC technique the walls can be colder by 25 to 30 °C but remain above ambient temperature. If walls are treated with PRC coatings, the asphalt can be 7°C hotter than without PRC technique, this is due to more solar radiation oriented toward asphalt by reflection on the walls. CAE has also collected data about the energy consumption for cooling buildings in Europe and in the world. The world share of cooling energy consumption of buildings should double from 2025 to 2050.

2 Modeling results - POLITO

POLITO (Politecnico di Torino) modelled the particular case of a conventional air-cooled vapor compression heat pump, enhanced by a passive daytime radiative cooling (PDRC) panels, used to cool a single-family dwelling consisting of two conditioned floors and an unconditioned attic with a total usable floor area of 174 m².

POLITO collaborated closely with CNR (Istituto Nazionale di Ottica, CNR-INO). CNT-INO provided downwelling spectral irradiance data from atmosphere and sky calculated using the modelling tools developed by CNR-INO in Task 2.2.

The configuration of the modelled system is shown in Figure 1. The PDRC system is used to get an overcooling of the refrigerant fluid after the condenser, which is cooled by external air ventilation. This configuration provides an additional cooling contribution to the refrigerant, thereby improving the seasonal energy efficiency rating (SEER) of the heat pump and reducing the overall electricity consumption.

The modeling of the overall thermal system (building, heat pump, PDRC panels) was done using MATLAB-Simscape environment.

Figure 1: DRC-enhanced heat pump, plant schematic

The full system, comprising the residential building and the PDRC-enhanced heat pump, was modeled over a representative cooling season in the northern hemisphere, spanning from June to August. Meteorological input data were sourced from the ERA5 Reanalysis dataset for the year 2023 [1]. Simulations were done for four distinct locations: Las Vegas (USA), Riyadh (Saudi Arabia), Madrid (Spain), and Turin (Italy), representing various Köppen–Geiger (KG) climate classifications. Las Vegas and Riyadh are characterized by a hot desert climate, with minimal annual precipitation and elevated summer temperatures. Madrid exhibits a hot-summer Mediterranean climate with dry summers, while Turin experiences a warm temperate oceanic climate with moderate summer temperatures. The average values of key atmospheric variables for each location during the simulation period are given in Table 1.

City	Latitude	Longitude	Air Temp. (°C)	Rel. Humidity (%)	Cloud Cover (%)	DWLWAR (W/m ²)	Wind Velocity (m/s)
Riyadh	24.7	46.7	36.7	11.4	13.1	384	3.0
Las Vegas	36.2	-115.1	29.2	23.7	25.9	357	2.4
Madrid	40.4	-3.7	26.4	39.1	25.0	355	2.5
Turin	45.0	7.7	23.7	58.6	46.2	362	2.1

Table 1: Information on the locations tested; air temperature, relative humidity, cloud cover, downwelling longwave atmospheric radiation (DWLWAR) and wind velocity are reported as average seasonal values

The thermal modellings were done considering real time varying climate parameters that is to say by integrating the effects of the thermal masses in the elements of the system. The total electrical power consumption considered was the sum of the electrical powers consumed by the heat pump compressor, the fans (condenser, fan coil units) and the circulation pumps. The integration over the selected simulation period gives the total electric energy consumption.

2.1 Parametric analysis

A parametric analysis was done regarding important parameters of the cooling system for the particular case of the Standard building under Las Vegas climate. The results are shown graphically in Figure 2. The detailed analysis of the influences of the parameters is given in **Annex 1**.

The results show that some parameters can be optimized to get a better efficiency and higher energy savings during the cooling season. This is the case for the area of the PDRC panels and the flow rate in the panels. The maximum energy saving is achieved for a surface area between 8-10 m² for the treated case.

Figure 2: Sensitivity analysis on panel net and radiative flux and subcooler temperature drop (a-c), specific and absolute electric energy savings (d-f) and seasonal EER increase, heat pump uptime decrease and relative energy savings (g-i). (a,d,g) The effect of panel array surface at $G_p/A_p=1.5$ L/min/m² and $\Delta T_{D,sc}=8^\circ\text{C}$. (b,e,h) The effect of subcooler size at $G_p/A_p=1.5$ L/min/m² and $A_p=8$ m². (c,f,i) The effect of panel specific flow rate at $\Delta T_{D,sc}=8^\circ\text{C}$ and $A_p=8$ m². These results are for a DRC system located in Las Vegas simulated with meteorological data for June-August. The shaded areas quantify the variability of the variables (as a standard deviation).

Five types of PDRC surfaces with different spectral shapes of spectral emissivity curves were tested. The relative spectral distributions of spectral emissivity of the five surfaces are shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 : Panel emissivity (ϵ_p) profiles of tested materials: Spectral Selective (SS), Broadband (BB), Spectral Selective with additional FIR emissivity (SSFIR), Commercial material 1 (C1) and Commercial material 2 (C2). I_{sol} is the normalized solar spectral radiance at 1.5 air mass [2]. I_{atm} is the normalized atmospheric spectral radiance obtained through the model in Ref. [3] at 20°C ambient temperature, 30% relative humidity and clear sky. The atmospheric spectral radiance values applied in the model correspond to the specific time and location under investigation.

The spectral emissivity curves for C1 and C2 PDRC materials were measured by CAE.

The results in terms of electric absolute and relative energy savings are presented in Figure 4.

The relative spreading of the electric energy savings results obtained are approximately 20% for the five PDRC materials tested. Even if the results are very specific to the cases tested and to the modelling parameters, this demonstrates that it is important to know the spectral emissivity curve of the PDRC material, in terms of level and spectral distribution, to compare efficiencies of PDRC materials.

Figure 4 : Effect of 5 different DRC emissivity profiles (SSFIR, BB, SS, C1 and C2) on electric absolute and relative energy savings. Parameters : $A_p = 10 \text{ m}^2$, $G_p/A_p = 1.5 \text{ L/min/m}^2$, $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, located in Las Vegas and simulated with meteorological data for June-August.

Electric energy savings related to the use of PDRC panels in association with a heat pump for four geographical locations and two buildings with different energy classes were calculated. The results are presented in Figure 5.

Riyadh, with the highest average ambient temperature, exhibited the greatest seasonal savings: 46.1 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC} for the Standard building and 38.0 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC} for the Modern building. Savings obtained for Las Vegas are 37.5 and 27.7 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}, Madrid: 20.1 and 12.5 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}, and Turin: 9.6 and 7.5 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}. The superior performance of the system in Riyadh and Las Vegas is attributed to both high cooling demand and favorable radiative cooling conditions (low humidity and cloud cover). Conversely, Turin showed the lowest savings due to low cooling demand and unfavorable summer climate, with high humidity and cloudiness. The relative energy savings for Standard buildings were -9.9 % (Madrid), -8.1 % (Las Vegas), -6.9 % (Turin) and -6.3 % (Riyadh). Notably, the locations achieving the highest relative energy savings were not those achieving the highest absolute savings, suggesting that relative energy reduction, commonly used as a performance metric, may not fully capture the benefits of radiative cooling. Absolute savings—normalized by DRC surface area or conditioned floor area—constitute a more representative measure of performance.

Figure 5 : Analysis of DRC panels performance by geographical location. (a) Electric energy savings at $A_p = 8$ m², $G_p/A_p = 1.5$ L/min/m² and $\Delta T_{DSc} = 12^\circ\text{C}$ for Modern and Standard building. (b) Electric energy savings at $A_p = 8$ m², $G_p/A_p = 1.5$ L/min/m² and $\Delta T_{DSc} = 12^\circ\text{C}$ for the Standard building across June-August.

2.2 Conclusions

Relative energy savings obtained by adding PDRC panels to the air cooling system of a single-family dwelling (two conditioned floors, unconditioned attic, floor area of 174 m²) are about 6% to 10%.

The spectral shape of the infrared emissivity curve of the PDRC panels has an effect on the efficiency of the global air cooling system. Spectral characterization of PDRC materials is therefore necessary to select the most efficient materials.

Some parameters of the global air cooling system (heat pump and PDRC panels) must be optimized to get better efficiency. That means that energy modeling is probably required for different types of buildings and different locations to optimize the performance of the global air cooling system assisted by a PDRC panels.

Combining PDRC panels with a classical air cooling system helps reduce electricity consumption during peak consumption periods.

One advantage of a heat pumps assisted by PDRC systems is that they can be used for thermal insulated buildings. The PDRC system is then just a supplement to a classical heat-pump installation. If the air cooling system (heat pump) already exists, which is quite often the case for very hot and sunny regions, it is quite easy to add a PDRC system.

The results of this particular study show that the total area of the PDRC panels can be limited to a few m². It is therefore technically feasible to use PDRC panels protected from convection to try to increase the electric energy savings by reference to unprotected panels. Energy modelling is still needed to quantify the gain with PDRC panels protected from convection.

2.3 References

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3 Modeling results – NKUA / building scale

NKUA modeled the potential energy savings at the building scale when using PRC systems in the building envelope for four types of buildings located in cities in the south of Europe and evaluated by radiation and thermal modelling the impact of the use of passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials at large scale in urban areas on the reduction of overheating at the ground level (air temperature).

3.1 Potential energy savings at the building scale when using PRC systems

The study was done using the modelling tools **DesignBuilder** software [1] as an interface for modelling the buildings (materials properties, occupancy schedules, HVAC systems, and internal thermal loads) and **EnergyPlus** [2] for dynamic modelling of heat transfers and energy consumptions of the whole buildings. For each building, the modelling was done for two scenarios, the "baseline configuration" employing conventional roofing materials and the "retrofit scenario" featuring the application of PDRC coating on the roof. EnergyPlus allows dynamic thermal modelling with hourly or sub-hourly energy balance calculations, incorporating the interactions between building envelope components, HVAC systems, internal loads, and external climatic conditions (temperature, solar radiation, wind). The TARP model was selected for inside surface convection, while the DOE-2 model was used for outside surface convection. The simulation time step was set to 6 timesteps per hour, providing sufficient resolution for capturing dynamic heat transfer processes and internal load fluctuations. Climate-specific simulations were conducted for each case study using hourly weather files corresponding to the nearest meteorological station of the respective climate zone (described in the following section). To assess sensitive zones for heating and cooling performance, the analysis relied on EnergyPlus outputs for key thermal variables (e.g., indoor air temperature, roof surface temperature) and energy metering results.

The **default constant emissivity model** in EnergyPlus is not capable of capturing the **spectral-dependent thermal emissivity (ϵ)** of cool roofing materials. Therefore, a **custom numerical model** was developed in MATLAB [3] to simulate the actual behavior of a passive daytime radiative cooling (PDRC) material based on its spectral emissivity characteristics. In the spectral-dependent model, a solar absorptance (SA) of 0.07 is assigned in EnergyPlus, corresponding to a solar reflectance (SR) of 0.93. The emissivity is initially set to $\epsilon = 0$ within EnergyPlus to isolate the radiative cooling contributions computed externally. To improve the accuracy of emissivity characterization, a **spectral-dependent radiative cooling model** was implemented to estimate the **net radiative heat flux (P_{PDRC})** from the roof surface in [W/m^2]. In this framework:

P_{ATM} [W/m^2] represents the atmospheric longwave radiation absorbed by the roof surface under clear-sky conditions,

P_{R} [W/m^2] denotes the outgoing radiation emitted by the roof surface,

P_{SUN} [W/m^2] is the absorbed portion of solar radiation, and

P_{CONV} [W/m^2] corresponds to the convective heat transfer between the roof surface and the ambient air.

These energy fluxes are schematically illustrated in Figure 6, which outlines the radiative and convective exchanges at the roof level. Each term is defined by a corresponding mathematical formulation, as presented in **equations 1–4**, following the methodology described in [4].

$$P_{\text{ATM}} = 2\pi \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin \theta \cos \theta \, d\theta \int_{7 \mu\text{m}}^{20 \mu\text{m}} I_{\text{BB}}(T_{\text{AMB}}, \lambda) \epsilon_{\text{R}}(\lambda) \epsilon_{\text{A}}(\theta, \lambda) d\lambda \quad (1)$$

$$P_R = 2\pi \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sin \theta \cos \theta \, d\theta \int_{7 \mu\text{m}}^{20 \mu\text{m}} I_{BB}(T_A, \lambda) \varepsilon_R(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (2)$$

$$P_{SUN} = \int_{0 \mu\text{m}}^{4 \mu\text{m}} \varepsilon_R(\lambda, \theta_{SUN}) I_{SUN}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (3)$$

$$P_{CONV} = h_c(T_A - T_S) \quad (4)$$

Where θ [rad] is the solar azimuthal angle, λ is the wavelength [m], T_A [K] and T_S [K] are outdoor environmental temperature and roof surface temperature respectively, ε_R is the PDRC material emissivity, that is equal to 0.889 in 7-13 μm and 0.3 outside this range, ε_A is the atmospheric emissivity evaluated as in Eq. 5, I_{BB} [W/m²·s·m] is the wavelength-dependent radiance of a blackbody with a temperature T [K] as in Eq. 6, I_{SUN} [W/m²·m] is the solar spectrum, h_c is the convective heat transfer coefficient on roof external surface.

$$\varepsilon_A = 1 - [t(\lambda)]^{\frac{1}{\cos \theta}} \quad (5)$$

$$I_{BB}(T, \lambda) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k_B T}} - 1} \quad (6)$$

where $t(\lambda)$ is the atmosphere transmittance, h equal to $6.62 \cdot 10^{-34}$ J·s is Planck's constant, k_B equal to $1.38 \cdot 10^{-23}$ J/K is Boltzmann constant and c equal to $3.0 \cdot 10^8$ m/s is the light speed in vacuum.

Figure 6. Energy flows into and through a PDRC layer

PDRC material heat flux P_{PDRC} is evaluated as in Eq. 7:

$$P_{PDRC} = P_{ATM} - P_R \quad (7)$$

Since EnergyPlus internally calculates both **solar radiation absorption (PSUN)** and **convective heat exchange (PCONV)**, these components are directly managed within the simulation engine. To account for the **net radiative cooling power** of the PDRC material (**PPDRC**, derived from Eq. 7), an **internal negative heat source** is introduced in the model. This source is positioned between the roof slab and an additional layer of material characterized by $\varepsilon = 0$ and $SA = 0.07$, corresponding to the real solar absorption of the PDRC surface. This configuration enables the injection of the PPDRC value as a customized cooling term within a specific construction layer, bypassing the default constant emissivity model of EnergyPlus and effectively implementing a **spectral-dependent emissivity ($\varepsilon = f(\lambda)$)**.

Because the **external surface temperature of the roof (T_s)** influences P_{PDRC} , an **iterative coupling** between MATLAB and EnergyPlus is required. The iterative procedure is structured as follows:

- **Initial Step:** T_s is set equal to its value in the baseline scenario (i.e., without PDRC).
- **Iteration:** MATLAB calculates a new P_{PDRC} based on the current T_s , which is then inserted into EnergyPlus.
- **Update:** EnergyPlus runs the simulation with the updated internal source and returns a new T_s .
- **Convergence Check:** The loop continues until the difference between two successive T_s values is less than **0.1 K**, as recommended in [5].

This iterative process ensures thermal consistency between the spectral model and the dynamic energy simulation. Within EnergyPlus, the **Energy Management System (EMS)** is configured to track and regulate

the roof surface temperature by controlling the internal cooling source. A schematic representation of the overall approach is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Flowchart of the coupled spectral emissivity-dependent model in MATLAB and EnergyPlus simulations

3.2 Modeled cases

Four buildings of different types in different locations were selected. Information about the four buildings studied are given in tables 4-7 and information about climatic data is given in Table 4 and air temperatures are shown graphically in Figure 8.

Type of building	Location	Main features	Heating, cooling modes
Multifamily building (MFB)	Marseille, France	Six-story residential block with flat roof, constructed in the period 2000 to present, total of 86 apartments.	Individual gas heaters, no active cooling system
Single-family house (SFH)	Varaždin, Croatia	Single-story dwelling with flat roof, constructed prior to 1970, one residential unit, gross floor area = 73.1 m ²	Electric heaters, no active cooling system
Detached house (DH)	Milan, Italy	Two-story building with flat roof, constructed prior to 1980, single residential unit. floor area = 86.5 m ² ,	Fuel gas boiler (efficiency = 0.82). no active cooling system
Detached house (DH)	Athens, Greece	Single-story building with flat roof, constructed between 1980 and 2000, single residential unit. floor area = 107.2 m ²	Fuel oil boiler (efficiency = 0.85). Air conditioning system powered by electricity (Energy Efficiency Ratio = 3)

Table 2 : Types and main features of building, location, heating/cooling modes

Figure 8. Annual outdoor air temperature for Marseille (A), Varaždin (B), Milan (C) and Athens (D)

CITY (NATION)	WEATHER DATA FOR ENERGYPLUS	OPERATING FUNCTIONING	
		HEATING PERIOD	COOLING PERIOD
Marseille (France)	MARSEILLE - FRA IWECC Data WMO#=076500	Beginning: 17/11 End: 13/03	Beginning: 14/06 End: 09/09
Varaždin (Croatia)	Varaždin.AP VA HRV SRC-TMYx WMO#=142460	Beginning: 01/11 End: 01/03	Beginning: 01/05 End: 01/09
Milan (Italy)	Milano-Linate - ITA IGDG WMO#=160800	Beginning: 15/10 End: 15/04	Beginning: 15/06 End: 15/09
Athens (Greece)	ATHENS - GRC IWECC Data WMO#=167160	Beginning: 01/11 End: 15/04	Beginning: 15/05 End: 15/09

Table 3. Cities chosen for simulations: weather data and heating/cooling periods

Multifamily building in Marseille

Geometrical features		
Exposure	Walls' area [m ²]	Windows' area per walls' area [%]
North	433.9	0
South	433.9	0
Est	868.0	46
West	868.0	46
Thermal features		
Element	Description	Thermal transmittance, U [W/m ² K]
Roof	20 cm concrete roof terrace and 8 cm polyurethane insulation	0.28
Ground-floor slab	20 cm concrete slab and 16 cm mineral wool insulation	0.19
Walls	20 cm concrete walls and 10 cm mineral wool insulation	0.28
Windows	Double glazing (6 mm), PVC frame	1.60

Table 4. MFB in Marseille: geometrical and thermal features

Figure 9. MFB in Marseille

Single-family house in Varaždin

Geometrical features		
Exposure	Walls' area [m ²]	Windows' area per walls' area [%]
North	23.8	8
South	23.8	12
Est	24.0	6
West	24.0	7
Thermal features		
Element	Description	Thermal transmittance, U [W/m ² K]
Roof	Wooden roof with mineral wool insulation	0.29
Ground-floor slab	Concrete slab with EPS polystyrene insulation	1.19
Walls	Stone walls with EPS polystyrene insulation	0.45
Windows	Double glazing (4 mm), PVC frame	2.37

Table 5. SFH in Varaždin: geometrical and thermal features

Figure 10. SFH in Varaždin

Detached house in Milan

Geometrical features		
Exposure	Walls' area [m ²]	Windows' area per walls' area [%]
North	65.1	0
South	65.1	8
Est	65.1	10
West	65.1	8
Thermal features		
Element	Description	Thermal transmittance, U [W/m ² K]
Roof	Pitched roof with brick concrete slab	2.19
Ground-floor slab	Concrete floor on soil	1.96
Walls	Solid brick masonry	1.47
Windows	Single glass, wood frame	4.84

Table 6. DH in Milan: geometrical and thermal features

Figure 11. DH in Milan

Detached house in Athens

Geometrical features		
Exposure	Walls' area [m ²]	Windows' area per walls' area [%]
North	24.0	0
South	24.0	16
Est	40.2	14
West	40.2	12
Thermal features		
Element	Description	Thermal transmittance, U [W/m ² K]
Roof	Conventional flat roof without insulation	3.11
Ground-floor slab	Concrete floor on soil	3.07
Walls	Double brickwork 10 cm, slightly ventilated air layer, unplastered on one side, 5 cm insulation	0.91
Windows	Double glazed (6 mm), aluminium frame	4.06

Table 7. DH in Athens: geometrical and thermal features

Figure 12. DH in Athens

In each building model, a zoning approach was applied by separating spaces into day and night zones, in order to account for the functional and occupancy-related differences throughout the day. Living spaces (kitchens, living rooms) are classified as day zones and are subject to higher internal heat gains from occupants, appliances, and artificial lighting. In contrast, bedrooms and other sleeping areas are defined as night zones with reduced internal loads. The main characteristics of each zone type are summarized in Table 8, while Figure 13 illustrates the annual schedules for occupancy, equipment use, and lighting. These schedules and internal load values are based on the guidelines provided by ASHRAE (American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers) [6], which ensures that the modelling parameters related to HVAC operation, thermal loads, and internal gains are consistent with internationally accepted practices for building energy simulations.

NIGHT - OCCUPATION	NIGHT - EQUIPMENT	NIGHT - LIGHT	DAY - OCCUPATION	DAY - EQUIPMENT	DAY - LIGHT
Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomBed_Occ, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 07:00, 1, Until: 08:00, 0.5, Until: 09:00, 0.25, Until: 22:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 0.25, Until: 24:00, 0.75, For: Weekends, Until: 07:00, 1, Until: 08:00, 0.5, Until: 09:00, 0.25, Until: 22:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 0.25, Until: 24:00, 0.75, For: Holidays, Until: 07:00, 1, Until: 08:00, 0.5, Until: 09:00, 0.25, Until: 22:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 0.25, Until: 24:00, 0.75, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;	Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomBed_Equip, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 07:00, 0.06993, Until: 08:00, 0.53497, Until: 09:00, 1, Until: 10:00, 0.53497, Until: 17:00, 0.06993, Until: 18:00, 0.30245, Until: 19:00, 0.53497, Until: 20:00, 0.76748, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.76748, Until: 24:00, 0.30245, For: Weekends, Until: 07:00, 0.06993, Until: 08:00, 0.53497, Until: 09:00, 1, Until: 10:00, 0.53497, Until: 17:00, 0.06993, Until: 18:00, 0.30245, Until: 19:00, 0.53497, Until: 20:00, 0.76748, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.76748, Until: 24:00, 0.30245, For: Holidays, Until: 07:00, 0.06993, Until: 08:00, 0.53497, Until: 09:00, 1, Until: 10:00, 0.53497, Until: 17:00, 0.06993, Until: 18:00, 0.30245, Until: 19:00, 0.53497, Until: 20:00, 0.76748, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.76748, Until: 24:00, 0.30245, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;	Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomBed_Light, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 07:00, 0, Until: 10:00, 1, Until: 19:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Weekends, Until: 07:00, 0, Until: 10:00, 1, Until: 19:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Holidays, Until: 07:00, 0, Until: 10:00, 1, Until: 19:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;	Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomLounge_Occ, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 18:00, 0.5, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.66667, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Weekends, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 18:00, 0.5, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.66667, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Holidays, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 18:00, 0.5, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.66667, Until: 24:00, 0, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;	Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomLounge_Equip, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 16:00, 0.06413, Until: 18:00, 0.53206, Until: 22:00, 1, Until: 23:00, 0.68804, Until: 24:00, 0.06413, For: Weekends, Until: 07:00, 0.06413, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0.34489, For: Holidays, Until: 07:00, 0.06413, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0.34489, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;	Schedule:Compact, Dwell_DomLounge_Light, Fraction, Through: 31 Dec, For: Weekdays SummerDesignDay, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Weekends, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: Holidays, Until: 16:00, 0, Until: 23:00, 1, Until: 24:00, 0, For: WinterDesignDay AllOtherDays, Until: 24:00, 0;

Figure 13. Night and day schedules for: occupation, equipment and light

FEATURE	NIGHT AND DAY ZONES
Occupancy density [people/m ²]	0.0215
Other equipment [W/m ²]	13.03
Domestic hot water consumption [l/m ² day]	1.067
Heating setpoint temperature [°C]: HVAC on/off	22/12
Cooling setpoint temperature [°C]: HVAC on/off	26/32
Minimum fresh air [l/s person]	2.36
Lighting power [W/m ² -100lux]	3.409

Table 8. Night and day zones main features

3.3 Results

Roof temperature results:

Multifamily building in Marseille (France)

Figure 14 illustrates the annual profile of roof surface temperature (T_s) for the two previously described scenarios: the baseline case (without PDRC, shown on the left) and the spectral emissivity-dependent model (with PDRC). Additionally, the right side of the figure compares T_s under the spectral emissivity-dependent model to the outdoor air temperature. The average T_s is 16.7 °C in the baseline scenario and 14.4 °C in the PDRC case, showing a temperature reduction of 2.3 °C. The standard deviation of T_s in the PDRC scenario is 7.7 °C, indicating reduced thermal fluctuations compared to the baseline.

Figure 14 : MFB in Marseille: roof outside face temperature with and without PDRC (left) and T_s vs outdoor air temperature (right)

Single-family house in Varaždin (Croatia)

Figure 15 presents the annual profile of roof surface temperature (T_s) for the two scenarios: the baseline case (without PDRC, left) and the spectral emissivity-dependent model (with PDRC). On the right, T_s from the spectral model is compared with the outdoor air temperature. The average T_s is 13.1 °C for the baseline and 6.9 °C for the PDRC case, indicating a temperature reduction of 6.2 °C due to the application of PDRC. The standard deviation in the PDRC scenario is 11.6 °C, reflecting higher thermal variability under this condition.

Figure 15 : SFH in Varaždin: roof outside face temperature with and without PDRC (left) and T_s vs outdoor air temperature (right)

Detached house in Milan (Italy)

Figure 16 illustrates the annual variation of roof surface temperature (T_s) for the two examined scenarios: the baseline (without PDRC) and the spectral emissivity-dependent model (with PDRC). The graph on the left depicts the temporal evolution of T_s throughout the year, while the right-hand graph compares T_s from the spectral emissivity-dependent model with the corresponding outdoor air temperature. The average T_s in the baseline case is 18.8 °C, whereas it decreases to 12.0 °C with the application of PDRC, indicating a significant reduction of 6.9 °C. The standard deviation of T_s in the PDRC case is 8.8 °C, highlighting a more stable thermal profile across the year.

Figure 16 : DH in Milan: roof outside face temperature with and without PDRC (left) and T_s vs outdoor air temperature (right)

Detached house in Athens (Greece)

Figure 17 presents the annual profile of roof surface temperature (T_s) for the two scenarios under analysis: the baseline case (without PDRC) and the spectral emissivity-dependent model (with PDRC). The left-hand graph illustrates the temporal evolution of T_s throughout the year, while the right-hand graph compares T_s from the PDRC-enhanced model with the corresponding outdoor air temperature. The average T_s is 22.3 °C in the baseline scenario and 16.6 °C with the application of PDRC, resulting in a notable temperature reduction of 5.7 °C. The standard deviation in the PDRC scenario is 7.7 °C, indicating a more consistent thermal behavior over time.

Figure 17 : DH in Athens: roof outside face temperature with and without PDRC (left) and T_s vs outdoor air temperature (right)

Summary Error. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. presents a comparative overview of the average, maximum, and standard deviation values of roof surface temperatures (T_s) across all case studies. These metrics are reported for both the baseline scenario (without PDRC) and the spectral emissivity-dependent model (with PDRC materials). The table enables a direct assessment of the thermal mitigation potential of PDRC across different climatic and architectural contexts.

In the actual state (Table 2), none of the buildings is equipped with a cooling system. Therefore, to enable a consistent and comparable evaluation across all case studies, it was assumed that each building operates with a standardized HVAC configuration: a gas boiler for heating and an air-to-air heat pump for cooling.

The system performance parameters—including generation, distribution, and emission efficiencies—are derived from the Minimum Requirements Decree of the Italian national energy performance legislation [7], and applied to a reference building operating under standard conditions. This approach ensures homogeneity in performance comparison and enables evaluation of the potential impact of PDRC materials on primary energy demand across different climates and building typologies.

Building-Location	Top floor		Whole building	
	Cooling needs	Heating needs	Cooling needs	Heating needs
	[kWh _t /m ² a]		[kWh _t /m ² a]	
MFB - Marseille	107.7	154.7	26.1	33.2
SFH - Varaždin	4.2	31.3	4.2	31.3
DH - Milan	30.5	160.3	20.7	131.5
DH - Atene	40.8	58.8	40.8	58.8

Table 9. Annual heating/cooling needs per conditioned floor area without PDRC materials application

Building-Location	Top floor		Whole building	
	Cooling needs	Heating needs	Cooling needs	Heating needs

	[kWh _t /m ² a]		[kWh _t /m ² a]	
MFB - Marseille	98.3	155.5	25.9	33.2
SFH - Varaždin	3.2	34.4	3.2	34.4
DH - Milan	10.8	180.0	10.0	137.9
DH – Atene	10.1	73.2	10.1	73.2

Table 10. Annual heating/cooling needs per conditioned floor area with PDRC materials application

Building-Location	Top floor		Whole building	
	ΔCooling needs	ΔHeating needs	ΔCooling needs	ΔHeating needs
MFB - Marseille	-8.7%	+0.5%	-0.8%	+0.0%
SFH - Varaždin	-23.8%	+9.9%	-23.8%	+9.9%
DH - Milan	-64.6%	+12.3%	-51.7%	+4.9%
DH – Atene	-75.2%	+24.5%	-75.2%	+24.5%

Table 11. Relative variation of annual heating/cooling needs in the PDRC case with respect to the case without PDRC

Building-Location	PEC [kWh _p /m ² a]		Δ PEC
	Without PDRC	With PDRC	
MFB - Marseille	64.0	63.9	-0.2%
SFH - Varaždin	44.0	47.3	+7.3%
DH - Milan	187.5	187.2	-0.1%
DH – Atene	109.1	103.2	-5.4%

Table 12. Annual primary energy consumption (PEC) for the whole building and variation in the PDRC application scenario with respect to the baseline scenario

3.4 Discussion

Energy consumption during the cooling season:

The use of PRC yield strong reductions of cooling needs for the detached single or two-story houses studied (-23.8% to -75.2%). The relative reductions of cooling needs are very high (-51.7% and -75.2%) for the two buildings with less insulated roofs. For the six-story residential block in Marseille, the relative cooling energy gain related to the use of PRC is low for the whole building but is -8.7% for the top floor.

Annual energy consumption:

Regarding the multifamily building (MFB) in Marseille, the application of PDRC materials has a negligible impact on the total primary energy consumption (PEC). This indicates that the reduction in cooling demand during summer is almost entirely counterbalanced by an increase in heating demand during winter.

In the case of the single-family house (SFH) in Varaždin, a net increase in total primary energy consumption is observed following the application of PDRC. This outcome is driven by a significant rise in winter heating needs, which is not compensated for by the relatively low reduction in cooling demand. Such results underscore that PDRC materials are not suitable in cold climatic conditions, where heating dominates the energy balance.

For the detached house (DH) in Milan, the overall energy impact of PDRC is practically neutral. Although the technology leads to a substantial reduction in cooling demand, this is largely offset by increased heating consumption, especially on the top floor.

Conversely, for the detached house in Athens, the application of PDRC results in a net reduction in primary energy consumption. The warmer climate of the region enhances the benefits of reduced cooling loads, while the increase in heating demand remains moderate, thus ensuring a positive energy balance.

These results confirm that PDRC materials are most effective in hot climates, such as that of Athens, where cooling energy savings dominate and lead to overall primary energy consumption reductions. In temperate climates like Marseille and Milan, the seasonal energy trade-off limits the net benefits, whereas in cold climates (e.g., Varaždin), the increased heating penalty makes the use of PDRC energetically counterproductive.

3.5 References

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4 Modeling results – NKUA / urban heat island

Urban overheating is defined as the excessive increase of ambient temperatures in urban areas compared to their rural surroundings due to anthropogenic activities, reduced vegetation and heat accumulation in materials. It constitutes one of the most pressing environmental challenges in contemporary cities due to health problems and economic losses related.

In Task 2.3 of PaRaMeTriC project, NKUA the potential impact of large-scale PRC implementation in reducing urban heat island intensity and related cooling energy loads, using microclimatic simulation tools

The research was conducted using the ENVI-met microclimatic simulation model, focusing on areas with pronounced urban overheating, and employing detailed data on local urban morphology. The analysis targets typical hot summer days. To assess the contribution of PRC materials (Scenario B) in mitigating heat and enhancing thermal comfort indices, results were compared with those obtained using conventional construction materials (Scenario A), commonly found in today's urban infrastructure.

The selected case study locations in Greece are Heraklion (Crete) and Neos Kosmos (Athens), both of which experience intensified urban overheating. Moreover, reliable meteorological datasets are available for these areas, enabling robust model validation. Specifically, radiation data from a micrometeorological tower in Heraklion were utilized for the empirical evaluation of the radiation balance. Based on this assessment, a microclimatic simulation was developed in ENVI-met, serving as a validation benchmark for the model.

4.1 Validation of ENVI-MET for calculation of reflected short-wavelength and emitted long-wavelength radiation

To validate ENVI-met model, the calculated radiation data were compared to observational data from the micrometeorological tower located in Heraklion. The comparison was performed at a height of 27 meters, corresponding to the radiometer's measurement level. Hourly values from the second simulation day (28/07/2021) were analyzed (Figure 18).

Figure 18 : Comparison between measured and simulated data in Heraklion for emitted and reflected radiation

The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was calculated for the base scenario—where both measured and simulated values are available—in order to quantify the model's performance. The MAE reflects the average deviation of the model from observed values and is expressed in W/m^2 . The MAE was calculated as 10.64 W/m^2 for reflected radiation and 23.20 W/m^2 for emitted radiation. Relatively to the mean radiation fluxes those errors are 9% and 5 % respectively for the reflected and for the emitted radiation.

Those results indicate that ENVI-met model performs satisfactorily in simulating radiation fluxes. Specifically, for reflected radiation, percentage deviations remain below 10% during midday hours. Larger discrepancies occur during early morning and late evening hours due to low solar angles, where even small absolute deviations (e.g., 10 W/m^2) correspond to large relative errors. For emitted radiation, the relative difference ranges from -1% to $+9\%$, with the maximum observed at 14:00. The absolute deviation varies between 5 W/m^2 at 10:00 and 47 W/m^2 at 17:00.

The results suggest that the ENVI-met model, when properly initialized, provides a reliable representation of radiation behavior in the selected urban environment.

4.2 Calculation of radiation fluxes with and without PRC coatings

The impact of the passive reflective coating (PRC) material was assessed by comparing radiation parameters between the conventional (base case) and PRC scenarios.

For reflected radiation, Figure 19 illustrates the comparison between the two cases. The maximum reflected radiation occurs at 14:00, coinciding with the peak of solar radiation. As expected, the PRC scenario exhibits significantly higher reflected radiation values, ranging from 5 W/m^2 at 07:00 to 339 W/m^2 at 14:00. The percentage increase in reflected radiation due to the PRC application ranges from 120% to 170%, demonstrating the high effectiveness of cool materials in enhancing urban surface reflectivity.

Regarding emitted radiation at a height of 27 meters (the radiometer location), the results also reveal clear differences between the two scenarios. The use of PRC materials leads to a general decrease in emitted longwave radiation, especially during midday hours. This reduction stems from the increased reflectivity and lower surface heat absorption, which contributes to cooling the urban environment and mitigating the urban heat island effect.

The percentage reduction in emitted radiation compared to the base case varies between 4% and 12%, with the maximum differences occurring around midday. Notably, during early morning hours (before 09:00), a slight increase in emitted radiation is observed in the PRC case, reaching up to $+10.8 \text{ W/m}^2$ at 08:00, likely due to accumulated nighttime cooling. After 08:00 and until midnight, the emitted radiation is reduced in the PRC scenario by 3 to 63.6 W/m^2 , indicating the material's persistent cooling effect throughout the day.

Figure 19 : Comparison of the performance of conventional and passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials in terms of reflected and emitted radiation, based on ENVI-met simulations at a height of 27 m

Validation of ENVI-met for calculation of air temperature

The second area of ENVI-met model evaluation involved the calculation of air temperature in Athens, focusing on Neos Kosmos district. The model’s output was compared to real measurements obtained from the Meteo weather station in the area.

The spatial layers used for the simulation in QGIS (geographic information system), including grid, buildings, 3D vegetation, and surface types, are depicted in Figure 20; the location of the Meteo station is marked with a pink dot. The simulation period spans from 27 July 2021, 06:00 a.m., to 29 July 2021, 06:00 a.m., representing typical summer conditions in the region.

Figure 20 : 2D and 3D visualization of Neos Kosmos area in ENVI-met (Spaces), including the QGIS-generated INX layers: (a) gridding, (b) vegetation, (c) buildings, and (d) surfaces.

To validate the temperature outputs, simulated air temperature was extracted at a height of 22 meters, corresponding to the height of the radiometer. Figure 21 presents the hourly temperature values for the second simulation day (28/07/2021), comparing measured and modeled data, along with the percentage difference.

Figure 21 : Comparison between measured and simulated air temperature values

The analysis reveals a consistent daily temperature pattern between measured and simulated data, with differences remaining within acceptable limits. The maximum absolute deviation is 2.5°C at 07:00, while the minimum is 0.06°C at 10:00. Importantly, the timing of the maximum temperature aligns in both datasets, indicating strong temporal accuracy of the model. To further quantify model accuracy, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was computed, yielding a value of 1.46°C, which is considered acceptable and confirms the ENVI-met model's ability to realistically simulate air temperature for this urban context and timeframe.

4.3 Evaluation of the impact of PRC Material on air temperature

To evaluate the impact of the passive cool roofing (PRC) material on air temperature, simulated data from ENVI-met were compared against real observations from the weather station. The comparison focused on the

air temperature at 22 meters, corresponding to the height of the station. Line graphs are presented showing the evolution of air temperature for both scenarios (conventional and PRC material) at 22 meters height (Figure 22). In addition, a 2D visualization (Figure 6) of air temperature was generated using Leonardo, which represents spatial temperature variations across the simulation domain through a color scale.

Figure 22 : Comparison of air temperature between the two scenarios, evaluated at the height of the meteorological station (22–24 meters).

The results indicate that the application of the PRC material results in lower air temperatures, with the maximum reduction reaching 0.92°C at 14:00 and the minimum difference being 0.04°C at 06:00. During the main part of the day (08:00–22:00), the temperature reduction ranges from 0.10°C to 0.09°C, while during the early morning and late evening hours (before 08:00 and after 22:00), the differences are smaller, between 0.05°C and 0.07°C. The cooling effect of passive materials is more pronounced during hours of high solar radiation.

Next, 2D color maps of air temperature at 22 meters are presented for 10:00 a.m., 1:00 p.m., and 10:00 p.m (Figure 23). Each map includes a legend on the right, indicating the temperature scale and the maximum and minimum values across the study area at each time step.

At 1:00 p.m., the difference between the maximum and minimum air temperature is the greatest (approx. 3°C), highlighting increased spatial variability and the effectiveness of cool materials in reducing localized heat accumulation. These visualizations confirm that passive cooling materials exhibit the strongest influence during morning and especially midday hours, while after sunset, their thermal impact becomes negligible. Finally, air temperature was also calculated at 2 meters above ground in order to evaluate the effect of rooftop passive cool materials on temperatures closer to pedestrian level (Figure 24). This allows for the assessment of the vertical extent of the cooling influence and its potential contribution to improved outdoor thermal comfort.

Figure 23 Spatial distribution of air temperature (2D color maps) at a height of 23 meters, for 10:00, 13:00, and 22:00

Figure 24 : Comparison of air temperature between the two scenarios and the corresponding percentage difference at 2 meters above ground level.

To further investigate the impact of passive cool roofing materials (PRC) on the urban thermal environment, two-dimensional visualizations of air temperature at 2 meters above ground level were produced using LEONARDO for three representative time points: 10:00 a.m., 1:00 p.m., and 10:00 p.m. (Figure 25). The results show that temperature differences between the conventional and PRC scenarios are most pronounced during midday, particularly in the 13:00–16:00 period. Despite this, the maximum reduction in pedestrian-level air temperature does not exceed 0.6°C, highlighting the limited cooling effect of rooftop interventions at ground level. The overall diurnal temperature trend remains similar in both scenarios.

In parallel, color maps of rooftop surface temperature (Figure 26) were also generated, corresponding to the time of maximum temperature divergence between the 2 scenarios. The PRC scenario exhibits a peak reduction of 0.615°C compared to the base case. The application of PRC material results in visibly lower surface temperatures and a more uniform distribution across building rooftops, which indicates reduced heat accumulation in the building envelopes.

This decrease in rooftop surface temperature contributes to reducing heat gain inside the buildings, thereby lowering cooling energy demand. Indirectly, it also aids in moderating the surrounding air temperature, enhancing outdoor thermal comfort, particularly during hot summer days and extreme heat events.

From a broader perspective, the integration of passive cool materials appears to be an effective urban heat island (UHI) mitigation strategy. However, their impact is maximized when used in conjunction with complementary bioclimatic design measures, such as: Green infrastructure (vegetation), Water features (fountains, ponds), Shading systems (pergolas, reflective canopies). These combined strategies enhance urban resilience, promote thermal well-being, and contribute to both physical and mental health, especially for vulnerable populations during heatwaves.

Figure 25 : Spatial distribution of air temperature (2D color visualizations) at a height of 2 m, for three representative times: 10:00, 13:00, and 22:00.

Figure 26 : 3D color map illustrating the surface temperature distribution at 13:00

4.4 Discussion

The present study evaluated the performance of the ENVI-met model in simulating key microclimatic parameters—namely shortwave and longwave radiation, as well as air temperature—in two representative urban areas in Greece: Heraklion and Athens. Furthermore, the thermal effect of an innovative passive cool roofing material (PRC) was investigated, focusing on its impact on radiation balance and air temperature.

Model validation against observational data showed that: For radiation fluxes, the percentage deviation during midday hours remained below 11%, demonstrating satisfactory agreement between simulated and measured values. This confirms the model's reliability in capturing radiation-related dynamics. For air temperature, the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was 1.46°C, a value considered acceptable for urban-scale microclimatic simulations. The model reproduced the diurnal temperature pattern well and captured the timing of daily maxima and minima.

However, it was also observed that model precision is sensitive to factors such as surface material characteristics and site-specific conditions, underlining the need for careful parameterization when simulating complex urban environments.

With regard to the performance of the PRC material, key findings related to radiation fluxes and temperatures include:

- A substantial increase in reflected solar radiation, particularly during midday hours, reaching values as high as 339 W/m² and a percentage increase of up to 170% compared to the conventional scenario.
- A reduction in emitted radiation, due to lower surface heat absorption.
- A moderate cooling effect on air temperature, with maximum reductions of 0.92°C at rooftop level and up to 0.6°C at pedestrian level, especially during peak solar radiation hours.
- The effectiveness of the PRC material diminishes significantly after sunset, indicating its limited contribution to nighttime cooling comparatively to conventional materials.

These results confirm that passive cool materials are most effective during periods of high solar irradiance and can participate in mitigating the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect, particularly when integrated into broader bioclimatic strategies.

4.5 Conclusions

NKUA modelled, for four different buildings at different locations in south of Europe, the potential energy savings at the building scale when using PRC system over the roof of the building. The relative reductions of cooling needs are very high (-51.7% and -75.2%) for the two studied single family buildings with less insulated roofs. For the top floor of a multifamily building in Marseille with a well-insulated roof the relative reduction of cooling needs over the cooling season is -8.7%. For a single family in Varaždin (Croatia), with a well insulated

roof the relative reduction of cooling needs over the cooling season is -23.8%. These results show that using PRC system on a roof allows reduction of cooling energy for cooling depending on the thermal resistance of the roof.

For the four buildings studied, the annual primary energy consumption (PEC) for the whole building is almost not affected by the use of PRC systems except for the building in Athens with a roof poorly insulated where there is a quite small relative gain in energy consumption over the year (-5.4% consumption). With PRC systems on the roofs, solar energy gains are reduced during the heating season almost practically cancelling the energy gains during the cooling season. To avoid the negative influence of PRC systems during the heating season in temperate climates where buildings are more thermal insulated, PRC systems should be combined with a controllable heat transfer system from the interior of the building to the surface of the envelope (for example by circulation of a heat transfer fluid). The system would then be more complex and require a greater investment. So future research should focus on integrating PDRC with dynamic or switchable materials, optimizing climate-specific configurations, and exploring hybrid systems that mitigate seasonal trade-offs.

The study showed that the use of PDRC materials on buildings can be a quite simple way to significantly reduce primary energy consumption for cooling poor thermal insulated buildings in the hotter regions in EU.

For the efficiency of using PRC systems at large scale in urban areas on the roofs of the buildings, the results obtained by NKUA showed that the air temperature at the ground level is only slightly reduced at the hotter hours of a hot day. The reduction calculated is about -0.65 °C at 2 m of the ground and -0.95 °C at an altitude of 22 m for an urban area in Greece at end of July. The calculations done didn't consider that the solar radiation not absorbed by the buildings covered by PRC systems is not dissipated as heat in the streets. This can give pessimistic results in terms of temperature reduction obtained at ground level. More complicated modelling would be probably needed to consider the heat transfers from the roofs of the buildings to the air in the streets.

5 Modeling results – CSIC

In Task 2.3 of PaRaMeTriC, CSIC had to :

- thermally model their experimental set-up with two cells used to test "Hydronic cooling system" and validate the model by comparison with experimental results.
- thermally model a typical building equipped with a hydronic cooling system and calculate the potential reduction of energy demand for cooling the building.

The present work develops and experimentally validates a numerical model for a residential building cooled by ceiling-mounted capacitive hydronic modules. These modules are supplied with chilled water produced by a field of sky-facing Daytime Radiative Cooling (DRC) panels. The model is employed to perform a sensitivity analysis on several design parameters of the system, including the number of operating hours, fluid flow rate, and the dimensions of both the DRC panels and hydronic modules, in two different locations: Madrid (Spain) and Rome (Italy). The results demonstrate that the proposed system can achieve high levels of thermal comfort while significantly reducing electricity consumption, by up to a factor of 40, compared to conventional compared to conventional air cooling (AC) systems.

CSIC was helped by **POLITO** for the development and use of the dynamic thermal modelling tool and by **CNR-INO** for getting climatic data and calculating downwelling spectral irradiances from sun or atmosphere.

5.1 Description of the technical configuration modeled

Figure 27 : Scenarios modeled. a) Hydronic cooling system with ceiling-mounted RCMs and external SRs. b) Hydronic cooling system with ceiling-mounted RCMs and rooftop SRs. c) Passive DRC material on the roof. Component legend: 1) building, 2) ceiling RCMs, 3) sky radiator (SR) covered with DRC material, 4) water tank, 5) circulation pump, 6) roof covered with DRC material. d) Full-scale demonstrator of a sky cooling-driven radiant-capacitive hydronic system located in Arganda del Rey (Madrid) [44].

Figure 28 : Net cooling flux q_{net} (Wm^{-2}) as a function of ambient-emitter temperature difference for a black paint and a commercial broadband DRC material under conditions of: a) high solar irradiance ($900 Wm^{-2}$), b) medium solar irradiance ($250 Wm^{-2}$), and c) no irradiance ($0 Wm^{-2}$). All simulations are conducted under clear-sky conditions with relative humidity values of 20% and 80 %, and a fixed panel heat transfer coefficient of $10 Wm^{-2} K^{-1}$. Panels d)–e) present the steady state emitter temperature as a function of solar irradiance for both a commercial DRC material and a black emitter, with results validated against experimental data reported in Ref. [44]. Panel f) shows the emissivity spectra of an ideal broadband emitter (dashed black), an ideal spectrally selective emitter (solid green), and a commercial broadband DRC material (solid blue). The shaded light grey region corresponds to the normalized solar emission spectrum at A.M. 1.5 [46], while the light blue region represents the normalized atmospheric spectral radiance under clear-sky conditions at $20\text{ }^{\circ}C$ ambient temperature and 30% relative humidity (obtained from the model in Ref. [47])

The principle of the cooling system and its integration in the building is shown in Figure 27. It comprises four main subsystems: building, ceiling Radiant Capacitive Modules (RCMs), external Sky Radiators (SRs), and water distribution system, which includes a buffer tank, circulation pump, and piping network. Unlike conventional ceiling cooling systems, the RCMs in this configuration are capacitive, featuring a serpentine heat exchanger embedded in a large volume of stationary water. This stationary water mass works as the primary thermal storage, as its capacity significantly exceeds that of the buffer tank working primarily as a pressure and temperature stabilizer. Locating the thermal storage within the ceiling, rather than in an externally exposed tank, enables direct thermal interaction with the building structural masses, which begin absorbing and redistributing cooling as soon as circulation starts. This configuration enhances the dynamic performance of the system, yielding a faster and more effective thermal response. A comprehensive discussion of the system design philosophy is provided in a related work [44]. The system is designed to exploit radiative cooling all day long. For that, the sky radiator is covered with a daytime radiative cooling material (DRC) with low solar absorptance and high emissivity in the atmosphere transparency spectral band.

Description of the elements

- **Building:** It is a modern two-story single-family residential building with a habitable area of 120 m² and a roof area of 67.7 m². Its favorable roof-to-volume ratio and moderate cooling demand provide adequate space to install a large enough sky radiator (SR) to meet cooling needs. The thermal properties of the building exceed the minimum national requirements set by the regulatory frameworks of Spain and Italy, as the selected locations in this study are Madrid and Rome. All components of the building envelope and internal masses, including external walls, internal thermal masses, ceiling, floor, and windows, are modelled as lumped elements. Each element is characterized by a thermal transmittance, heat capacity and dynamic thermal behaviour. Data used in this study are sourced from authoritative publications on European building sector [49] and national standards [50, 51].
- **Radiant Capacity Modules (RCMs):** The ceiling RCMs comprise galvanized steel enclosures containing approximately 50 L of stationary water cooled via heat exchange with a copper coil in which the water previously cooled by sky radiators is flown. The RCMs are connected in parallel to constitute the radiant capacitive ceiling system. Thermal exchange between the RCMs and the building occurs through natural convection with the indoor air, radiative heat transfer with the floor and the vertical walls, and conductive heat transfer through the top surface in direct contact with the structural ceiling. The primary novelty of this study lies in the integration of DRC module within a hydronic cooling system.
- **Sky Radiators (SRs):** Sky radiators consist of flat-plate panels with integrated parallel channels and a nominal surface area of 2.27 m². Each panel comprises a polypropylene plate through which water flows within multiple parallel channels. A DRC film is applied to the sky-facing surface, while the underside is insulated to minimize thermal losses. All radiators are connected in parallel.

Energy balance of Sky Radiators

The energy balance equation of sky radiators is :

$$Q_p - Q_{sol} - Q_{atm} - Q_{non-rad} - Q_{net} = C_p \frac{dT_p}{dt}$$

where, Q_p is the radiative flux emitted toward sky and atmosphere, Q_{sol} is the absorbed solar flux calculated for an air mass of 1.5, Q_{atm} is the radiative flux absorbed coming from atmosphere, $Q_{non-rad}$ is the sum of the convective heat flux and conductive heat fluxes entering the panels, Q_{net} is the net heat flux, C_p is the heat capacity of the sky radiators, dT_p is the panels temperature and t is time. In the relation, the net heat flux is positive when heat leaving the panels is higher than heat gained by the panels.

The radiative power emitted by the panel is calculated using the classical model and considering the directional spectral emissivity. The thermal radiation coming from atmosphere and absorbed by the cooling panels is calculated using the Longwave Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM LW) [52], [53] for calculating the spectral hemispherical downwelling longwave atmospheric irradiance (DWLWAR) at the surface. The influence of clouds cover is considered. Sixteen spectral bands are considered for spectral modelling of infrared radiations. For $Q_{non-rad}$ heat flux, only convection is considered.

The convective heat transfer coefficient is given by relation:

$h_p = 8.3 + 2.5 \frac{u}{u_0}$, where u is the wind velocity and $u_0 = 1 \text{ m.s}^{-1}$ is a constant.

Meteorological data: The calculation were done for the cooling season (June to September) and for two locations: Madrid (40.25°N, 3.50°W) and Rome (42.00°N, 12.50°E). The four-month period was selected based on the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) reported in PVGIS, developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre [54], constructed according to ISO 15927-4 standards [55]. Following TMY selection, the corresponding hourly meteorological variables were obtained from the ERA5 reanalysis [56, 57], specifically: ambient air temperature at 2 m was used; dew point temperature at 2 m was used for relative humidity; soil temperature at 28–100 cm depth was used as ground temperature; wind velocity at 10 m and average surface downwelling shortwave radiation flux was used as solar irradiance.

The locations of Madrid and Rome were selected based on two main considerations. First, Spain and Italy are among the most favorable regions in Europe for radiative cooling applications [59]. Second, the two cities exhibit different climatic conditions, allowing the experimental setup to be evaluated under varying weather scenarios. According to the updated Koppen–Geiger classification [60], Rome has a hot-summer Mediterranean climate, with dry summers and mild winters (Csa climate type). Madrid, instead, is situated on the boundary between the Csa climate and the BSk climate type, the latter corresponding to a cold semi-arid climate with hot summers.

5.2 Results

Model validation

The model was first successfully validated on the full-scale demonstrator shown in Figure 27 and located at Instituto de Ciencias de la Construcción Eduardo Torroja in Arganda del Rey (40.314°N, 3.482°W) near Madrid. The demonstrator, experimental setup, and acquired data are comprehensively described in [44]. The demonstrator consists of a small building (8.8m×7.0m×2.9 m), divided into three thermal zones: two rooms and a lobby. One room, equipped with the RCMs, is designated as the experimental cell (EC), while the other is the control cell (CC) and remains unconditioned. Externally, the system includes five parallel-connected SRs and a thermal storage unit. Additionally, smaller square samples (10 cm × 10 cm) of DRC and non-DRC materials, not connected to the hydraulic system, were installed and sensorized. The model validation was conducted using two experimental series, lasting five days: Series 1 (20/08–24/08/2024) and Series 2 (08/08–12/08/2024). In Series 1, the SRs were coated with a commercial DRC material (SpaceCool Film Silver), while in Series 2, the panels were uncoated, exposing the black polypropylene surface to the sky, to act as a night time-only radiative cooling material. In both cases, the circulation pumps operated from 10:00 PM to 8:00 AM. Validation was performed over the final four days of each series, excluding the first day to smooth the errors generated from the unknown initial conditions.

Figure 29a and b compare measured and simulated temperatures of the EC and CC for Series 1 and 2, respectively. The results demonstrate high agreement, with mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 0.67% and 0.64% for the CC and 0.70% and 0.86% for the EC. In both cases, the root mean square error (RMSE) remains below 0.3 °C. Figure 29c and d present the RCM temperature comparisons for Series 1 and 2, yielding respectively. Figure 29 e and f report the surface temperatures of the passive square samples for Series 1 and 2, featuring the DRC material and black polypropylene, respectively. The MAPE values are 5.58% and 4.19 %, with RMSE values of 1.4 °C and 2.2 °C. These results are consistent with other studies [61] and validate the DRC material model. The DRC sample remains consistently below ambient temperature throughout the day, including periods of peak solar irradiance. Figure 29g and h compare simulated net fluxes of the SRs with experimentally derived values, including uncertainty. The model predictions fall within the uncertainty bounds. MAPE values are approximately 10% for both series, even though the results are largely influenced by the discrepancies at the initial peak due to system startup. To provide a more comprehensive assessment, IOA is also considered, yielding values of 0.97 for Series 1 and 0.95 for Series 2. Overall, the results from both experimental series confirm the validity of the model for the building, RCMs, and SRs.

Figure 29 : Model validation against experimental results from the full-scale demonstrator in Ref. [44]. Panels a), c), e), and g) correspond to Series 1 (DRC emitter), while panels b), d), f), and h) correspond to Series 2 (black emitter). a–b) Temperature of the EC and CC. c–d) Water temperature in the RCMs. e–f) Surface temperature of the 20 × 20 cm² material samples. g–h) Net radiative flux of the panels.

Exploitation of the model for optimization of the technical configuration

The validated model is employed to assess the impact of a DRC-driven hydronic cooling system on a full-scale single family building during a TMY cooling season in the Madrid climate. The analysis includes a performance comparison with an identical system using a conventional nighttime emitter coated with a black paint (broadband infrared thermal emissivity of 0.9 and a solar reflectivity of 0.1). Figure 30 presents the effect of

varying the number of charging (pumping) hours on the overall performance of the cooling system. Charging hours denote the number of hours per day during which water is circulated through the closed loop connecting the SRs and RCMs. The minimum number of charging hours evaluated is 10, which includes all nighttime and low-irradiance hours in Madrid, from 10:00 PM to 8:00 AM. The pumping period is then progressively extended in 1 h-steps, expanding the time at both ends. Three DRC materials are included in the test: a commercial DRC emitter, an ideal BB emitter, and an ideal SS emitter. Their emissivity profiles are shown in Figure 28f. These simulations are carried out for a constant number of SRs and RCMs, set respectively to 25 and 60. These values are chosen because they are able to ensure a suitable comfort level in the building and lie reasonably close to the optimal working conditions of the plant for the building located in Madrid.

Figure 30–b displays the energy removed by the RCMs over the entire cooling season (June–September), with the system operating at flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. These flow rates are normalized by the area of the SRs, which is essential for correctly scaling the total flow within the system according to the emitter surface area, ensuring effective water cooling in each panel. The energy removed by the RCMs is a representative figure of merit for evaluating the effectiveness of the cooling system. When using the black emitter, the system achieves its peak seasonal energy removal at 11 and 10 pumping hours for the flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. In contrast, the use of a commercial DRC emitter results in a shift of the optimal operating window to 13 and 12 hours, enabling a two-hour extension in both cases. This expansion reflects the enhanced radiative performance of the emitter, particularly during early morning and late evening hours. Ideal BB and SS emitters demonstrate an even greater impact, allowing the optimal pumping duration to extend by three hours under both flow rate scenarios. In terms of relative performance improvement, the commercial DRC emitter increases total seasonal energy removal by +6.2% compared to the black emitter. The ideal BB and SS materials further improve energy removal by +10.3% and +6.3 %, respectively.

The curve corresponding to the black emitter declines as soon as the pumping period extends into daytime hours. This behavior is attributed to the significant heating of the black surface due to solar irradiance. Although DRC materials can ideally maintain subambient temperatures even under intense solar radiation, their performance also deteriorates beyond 13–14 pumping hours, depending on the flow rate. During high-irradiance periods, while the RCM water is still being cooled by the SRs, the outlet temperature may remain above the internal temperature of the building. As a result, the water, despite being cooled, is no longer effective in extracting heat from the indoor environment. Consequently, the total energy removed by the RCMs decreases. As shown in Figure 30–d, higher flow rates generally result in increased cooling fluxes. This is due to the higher average temperature of the SRs, which enhances radiative emission in accordance with the Stefan–Boltzmann law. Conversely, lower flow rates promote greater subcooling of the thermal fluid. As long as the fluid remains colder than the building environment, higher subcooling enables greater thermal energy extraction. This trade-off explains why, despite higher cooling efficiency at 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², the total energy removed and, therefore, the actual cooling effect, is lower compared to a flow rate of 0.25 L min⁻¹ m⁻². This highlights the critical importance of selecting an appropriate flow rate in systems without active cooling components such as heat pumps or HVAC units. The optimal flow rate maximizing thermal energy removal is a function of the design of the hydronic system, specifically the surface areas of the SRs and RCMs. However, provided the SR surface is not significantly undersized, the optimal flow rate consistently lies within the range of 0.2 to 0.3 L min⁻¹ m⁻². This finding is corroborated by extrapolations on the demonstrator unit, which also shows an optimal flow rate within the same range across different meteorological conditions, and by other studies [62]. Figure 30–f presents the average, minimum, and maximum indoor temperatures. The DRC materials yield lower average temperatures than the black emitter, with performance differences increasing at longer pumping durations.

Lower flow rates (0.25 L min⁻¹ m⁻²) result in reduced mean, minimum, and maximum temperatures compared to 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻². The minimum temperature is reached at 11 and 10 pumping hours for the black emitter, 13 and 12 for the commercial DRC, and 14 and 13 for the ideal BB and SS, respectively. Figure 30g–h show the monthly energy removed by the RCMs and the average SR flux, respectively, under optimal pumping durations. DRC materials extend the effective cooling window throughout the season. The ideal BB consistently outperforms the commercial DRC and ideal SS. Additionally, performance at 0.25 L min⁻¹ m⁻² is superior to 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻² across all months. The highest relative improvement over the nighttime emitter occurs in June (+6.5% for the commercial DRC, +10.9% for the ideal BB), and the lowest in September (+5.0% and +8.6 %, respectively). Figure 30g–h also demonstrate that, in hydronic cooling systems of this type, higher net cooling fluxes do not necessarily indicate a greater amount of energy removed from the indoor environment. This is because net cooling fluxes do not account for the extent of sub-ambient subcooling achieved by the

circulating water within the panel, which is the primary indicator of useful indoor cooling. Moreover, under the same atmospheric conditions, greater sub-ambient subcooling is associated with lower average water temperatures in the SRs, which in turn leads to reduced net heat fluxes.

RCMs and SRs sizing

A sensitivity analysis is required to determine the optimal sizing of the RCMs and SRs. Designing this system primarily involves determining the optimal surface areas for the SRs and RCMs. Ideally, both surfaces should be minimized while still ensuring continuous thermal comfort in the building.

To quantify thermal comfort, a metric called comfort indicator (CI) is introduced. This indicator measures the fraction of time during which the average indoor air temperature of the building (T_b) remains within a predefined target range, delimited by a minimum and a maximum target temperature T_{min}^* and T_{max}^* . It is defined using the indicator function:

$$\chi(t) = 1, \text{ if } T_{min}^* \leq T_b(t) \leq T_{max}^* \text{ and } \chi(t) = 0, \text{ otherwise}$$

$$\text{The comfort indicator is then given by: } CI = \frac{1}{t_{tot}} \int_0^{t_{tot}} \chi(t) dt ,$$

where t is time and t_{tot} is the total simulation time.

The DRC-based hydronic system closely resembles a naturally ventilated configuration as it lacks active components for air circulation. Moreover, while the DRC-hydronic system can be actively switched on or off, its performance cannot be precisely controlled via a setpoint, as it depends heavily on atmospheric conditions. ASHRAE-55 standard provides a method for defining comfort zones in buildings without mechanical ventilation [63, 64]. Applying this method using the average ambient temperature for August, the hottest month in Madrid according to TMY data, yields a comfort range of 23.8 °C to 28.8 °C. August is selected as it represents the most demanding thermal conditions. To be conservative, the upper bound of the comfort range was reduced to 27 °C. The lower bound T_{min}^* was not imposed, to assess the natural cooling limits of the DRC system and also because the system can simply be switched off in case the indoor temperatures become excessively low.

To determine the optimal sizing of SR and RCM surface areas, extensive simulations were conducted for the month of August in Madrid. The simulations were performed using the commercial DRC emitter, a flow rate of 0.25 L min⁻¹ m⁻², and 13 pumping hours, identified as optimal in previous analyses. Various combinations of RCM and SR areas were tested, and results are presented as color maps in Figure 31, where the areas of SRs and RCMs are normalized relative to the floor area of the building.

Figure 31a shows the variation of the comfort index. In general, there is not a defined configuration maximizing CI; instead, CI increases monotonically with both SR and RCM surface areas. A comfort of about 100% is achieved for a minimum SR coverage of 60% (with 60% RCMs coverage). If the acceptable CI is set to 90 %, the configuration that minimizes simultaneously the total surface area of RCMs and SRs (i.e., the Pareto-optimal point) is found at approximately 47% RCM and 53% SR coverage. This corresponds to about 70 RCMs (56.7m²) and 28 SRs (63.6m²).

Figure 31b presents the variation of average SR flux. The flux increases with RCM area and decreases with SR area. This inverse relationship with SR area arises because, at a fixed RCM size, increasing the SR area distributes the removed heat over a larger surface. As a result, the temperature of each SR decreases, leading to a reduction in radiative flux due to the lower surface temperature.

Figure 31c-d illustrate the impact of the hydronic cooling system on the building. Specifically, panel c) presents the average reduction in indoor air temperature achieved in the building relative to the same building without the hydronic cooling system (i.e., the cooling effect). Panel d) displays the specific energy removed, defined as the daily thermal energy dissipated by the RCMs, normalized by the surface area of the SRs. The cooling effect increases with both SR and RCM area, similar to the trend observed in the comfort index. In contrast, the energy removed follows a trend similar to that of average SR flux: it increases with RCM area and decreases with SR area. This is because higher RCM coverage and smaller SR surfaces result in higher average SR temperatures and, consequently, higher radiative fluxes. The absolute energy removed, on the other hand, follows a different trend, analogous to that of the cooling effect. Figure 31e-f show the relative improvement in comfort index for hydronic systems using a commercial DRC and an ideal BB emitter, respectively, compared to an identical system operating with a nighttime emitter (black emitter). In all cases, the systems operate at their respective optimal number of pumping hours. For both cases, the maximum improvement is observed at

an SR coverage of approximately 30% (corresponding to about 15 SRs), with gains of +8.7% for the commercial DRC and +13.2% for the ideal BB.

Figure 30: Analysis of pumping hours in a single-family building in Madrid using a commercial DRC emitter, an ideal BB emitter, an ideal SS emitter, and conventional black paint. The number of SRs and RCMs are kept constant, respectively to 25 and 60. a–b) Energy removed by the RCM operating at flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. c–d) Average SR flux at flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. e–f) Mean, maximum, and minimum indoor air temperatures with SR flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. Mean values are indicated by the markers, while minimum and maximum temperatures define the extent of the bars. g–h) Monthly energy removed by RCMs and average flux, respectively, under optimal conditions (i.e., at the number of pumping hours that maximizes energy removal) for flow rates of 0.25 and 1 L min⁻¹ m⁻². In panels a,b,e and f, the optimal values for each material are marked with an asterisk.

Figure 31 : SR and RCM sizing analysis for a single-family building in Madrid during August (TMY). a) Comfort index. b) Average SR flux. c) Average indoor temperature reduction compared to a passive building (no hydronic cooling). d) Specific thermal energy removed by RCMs. e) Comfort index improvement relative to a nighttime radiative cooling system. f) Comfort index improvement relative to a nighttime radiative cooling system, using the ideal BB material. All panels, except f), refer to the commercial DRC emitter.

Effect of plant configuration

The analysis is further extended by evaluating the performance of the DRC-hydronic cooling system under three scenarios (external SRs, rooftop SRs and DRC-roof) and at two selected locations: Madrid and Rome. The initial scenario involves the installation of SRs on external building surfaces (Figure 27a). The second scenario considers the installation of SRs directly on the building rooftop (Figure 27b). In the third scenario, the building is equipped with a DRC-roof. In this case, no active components are employed, and the building roof is entirely covered with a passive DRC material, as illustrated in Figure 27c. For all the configurations analyzed, the roof is assumed to be perfectly flat. To ensure consistency and comparability across the scenarios, the roof is considered to be entirely covered by the DRC technology, either in the form of SRs or as a continuous passive coating. According to the reference description of the two-story building, the total available roof area is 67.7m^2 , which, in the case of SR deployment, corresponds to approximately 29 SRs. External and rooftop SR configurations were tested using the same number of RCMs: 70 units (corresponding to a coverage of approximately 48 %).

Comparison across locations and configurations

Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. a and b present the average, maximum, and minimum indoor temperatures for the three analyzed configurations for the buildings located in Madrid and Rome, respectively. While the buildings in both locations share the same habitable surface area, they differ slightly in thermal insulation in accordance with national standards. In both locations, the configurations employing SRs exhibit comparable performance, with the rooftop SRs demonstrating slightly lower indoor temperatures across

the cooling season. Specifically, the average seasonal indoor temperatures achieved are 23.78 °C and 23.49 °C in Madrid, and 23.65 °C and 23.55 °C in Rome, for the external and rooftop SRs, respectively. In all cases, these values remain consistently below the adopted maximum thermal comfort threshold of 27 °C. In contrast, the passive DRC-roof configuration demonstrates limited cooling performance, with average seasonal temperatures exceeding the comfort limit: 28.13 °C in Madrid and 27.60 °C in Rome. **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.** c and d show the seasonal comfort index for the three configurations (color bars), along with the relative improvement over a reference fully passive building with a conventional roof (squares). Once again, the rooftop SR configuration slightly outperforms the external SRs. In Madrid, the seasonal CI values are 92.0% and 96.4% for external and rooftop SRs, respectively; in Rome, the values are 96.7% and 97.4 %, respectively. The relative CI improvement with respect to the reference case is +64.0% and +68.4% in Madrid, and +59.1% and +59.8% in Rome, for external and rooftop SRs, respectively. Of particular note is the monthly breakdown of relative comfort improvements: in Madrid, the external SR configuration achieves the highest improvement in July (+81.9 %), while the rooftop SRs peak in August (+88.3 %). In Rome, both configurations attain their maximum monthly improvement in August, with values of +90.3% and +90.6% for external and rooftop SRs, respectively. The consistently high seasonal CI values, always above 90% and approaching 100 %, demonstrate the effectiveness of the DRC-based hydronic cooling system in delivering thermal comfort under the examined climatic conditions and building typologies. These results confirm that the SR surface area was appropriately sized to meet the thermal load requirements of both locations. In particular, limiting the SR extension to the roof area is sufficient to ensure suitable comfort levels.

On the other hand, the DRC-roof configuration alone fails to provide acceptable thermal comfort, with CI values of only 34.2% in Madrid and 40.6% in Rome. While the DRC-roof is inadequate as a stand-alone cooling solution, it can contribute to significant reductions in electricity demand when integrated with active cooling systems [14–21]. As previously observed, the rooftop SR configuration combines the active cooling effect of external SRs with the enhanced solar reflectivity of a DRC-roof during daytime hours. However, the resulting comfort improvement is not a simple superposition of these two effects. In fact, the additional benefit of rooftop SRs over external SRs, in terms of comfort index, is relatively modest: +4.4% in Madrid and +0.6% in Rome. The primary reason for this limited improvement lies in the thermal insulation characteristics of the roof. Installing SRs directly on the roof introduces an additional insulating layer, mainly due to the water contained within the panels, which reduces the inward to outward heat flow, particularly during nighttime. This behavior is analogous to the reduced effectiveness of radiative cooling roofs when roof thermal insulation is increased, as discussed for instance in Ref. [15].

Considerations on the energy efficiency of the system

To assess the overall energy performance of the hydronic cooling system through a single performance indicator, an approach analogous to that used for mechanical refrigeration systems can be adopted. Specifically, in the case of heat pumps in cooling mode, the Seasonal Coefficient of Performance (*SCOP*) is defined as the ratio between the useful thermal effect— namely, the energy extracted by the evaporator to provide cooling—and the electrical energy consumed by active components such as the compressor and fans. A similar concept can be introduced for the DRC-hydronic system, where the useful effect is represented by the thermal energy removed by the RCMs (E_{RCM}), and the energy input corresponds to the electricity consumed by the circulation pump (E_{pump}), which is the only active component of the system. Accordingly, an equivalent *SCOP* for the hydronic system is defined as:

$$SCOP = \frac{E_{RCM}}{E_{pump}}$$

The quantity E_{RCM} is determined through a thermal energy balance on the RCMs, while E_{pump} is calculated based on the water flow rate, pressure losses in the circuit, pump efficiency and working time.

Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata. e and f present the monthly values of E_{RCM} and the corresponding *SCOP* for Madrid and Rome, respectively. The energy removed by the RCMs remains relatively stable over the cooling season in both locations. In Madrid, the average monthly energy removed is 830 kWh_{th} for the external SR configuration and 812 kWh_{th} for the rooftop SR configuration. In Rome, the corresponding values are 705 kWh_{th} and 691 kWh_{th}, respectively. The resulting *SCOP* values are proportional to the values of E_{RCM} , since the energy consumed by the pump is primarily determined by the total pumping time, which is roughly constant across all scenarios. Madrid achieves the highest *SCOP* values: 152 for external SRs and 149 for rooftop SRs. In Rome, the values are slightly lower, at 129 and 127, respectively.

A first observation concerns the magnitude of these SCOP values. For reference, the average SCOP of conventional air-to air cooling systems in the Spanish building sector is approximately 3.8 [65]. This means that the DRC-based hydronic system delivers a SCOP up to 40 times higher than conventional AC systems. This remarkable performance is primarily attributed to the low electricity demand of the system, with the circulation pump being the only active component. These SCOP values could be further improved by enhancing the thermal insulation of the water distribution pipelines. Another point of interest is the slightly lower SCOP observed for rooftop SR configurations compared to external SRs. This difference arises because the rooftop DRC layer reduces solar heat gains, thereby decreasing the overall cooling demand and, in turn, the energy removal by the RCMs. Moreover, SCOP can serve as a useful monthly performance metric for evaluating radiative cooling effectiveness. In both Rome and Madrid, the highest SCOP values are recorded in June and September, months typically characterized by favorable conditions for radiative cooling [59]. By contrast, in July and August, radiative cooling is significantly hindered by high ambient temperatures and increased convective heat gains. However, it is important to clarify that, although the SCOP has been defined in a manner similar to that of heat pumps, hydronic DRC-based cooling systems differ significantly from heat pumps. The latter are well-established technologies that enable precise indoor temperature control across all climates and, unlike DRC-based systems, are less heavily influenced by external weather conditions.

5.3 Discussion

In the previous analysis, the DRC-based hydronic cooling system has been demonstrated to be an effective, nearly passive solution for achieving adequate thermal comfort levels in both Madrid and Rome. The system provides substantially higher comfort indices compared to a passive DRC-roof configuration and achieves significantly greater SCOP values than conventional mechanical cooling systems. Nevertheless, the implementation of this technology may encounter certain limitations, most notably, the spatial requirements of the SRs and the issue of condensation.

The surface area required for SRs in such systems can be relevant and may exceed the area available for a typical residential building. As previously discussed, one potential mitigation strategy involves relocating the SRs to the rooftop, thereby taking advantage of the additional albedo effect. However, even rooftop areas may prove insufficient in locations with high cooling demands or in buildings with low roof-to-volume ratios. In general, this type of system is best suited to single-story buildings with large roof surfaces, such as warehouses, while its application in multi-story buildings (beyond two stories) is likely to be more challenging. In the case of the two-story building considered in this study, the required SR surface to achieve acceptable comfort levels was approximately equal to the total roof area. Furthermore, rooftop SR installation may compete with other rooftop technologies, such as photovoltaic or solar thermal systems, thereby posing additional constraints. To address these challenges, the system configuration was further optimized to reduce the total SR area. A straightforward, yet effective, strategy involves improving the thermal insulation of the piping network, which is otherwise subject to considerable convective heat losses. Figures 7a and b present the comfort index map and the indoor cooling effect, respectively, for varying numbers of SRs and RCMs in Madrid, under the assumption of a 90% reduction in pipe thermal losses compared to the previous analyses. This reduction can be achieved by adopting approximately 35mm of standard polyurethane insulation. As before, the Pareto-optimal configurations minimizing the combined surface areas of SRs and RCMs was identified. This improvement yields notable benefits: in Madrid, the required SR surface is reduced by approximately 9% (equivalent to 4–5 fewer SRs).

Figure 32c-d present the comfort index map and the indoor cooling effect, respectively, for Madrid under the combined effect of improved pipe insulation (90% loss reduction), enhanced window shading and improved nighttime ventilation. In the base case, only the shading provided by window recesses was considered. Here, an improved scenario assumes that 80% of direct solar radiation is blocked throughout the entire season through the use of window sun shadings. Additionally, the building is assumed to be naturally ventilated, incorporating vents designed to enable wind-driven ventilation. This strategy is represented in the simulation by a constant nighttime (10:00 PM to 8:00 AM) air change rate of 5 air changes per hour (h^{-1}). Although actual ventilation rates in wind-driven systems vary with wind speed and direction [66], a constant rate was used here to evaluate the potential benefits of effective nighttime ventilation. These aforementioned improvements, addressing both the hydronic system and building physics, result in a drastically reduced coverage requirement: 17% for RCMs and 19% for SRs. This demonstrates that the DRC-based hydronic system can be particularly effective in modern, well-insulated and naturally-ventilated buildings equipped with high-performance solar shading. Another potential limitation of the DRC-based hydronic cooling system, as with

other hydronic technologies reported in the literature, concerns condensation [42]. Under conditions of high relative humidity, the surface temperature of DRC elements may fall below the ambient dew point, leading to condensation of atmospheric moisture. To evaluate this risk, an analysis was conducted to quantify condensation occurrence across the different configurations studied. The results indicate that condensation on the RCMs does not occur in either Madrid or Rome, at least for the considered case studies. Regarding the external DRC surfaces, the impact of condensation in Madrid, characterized by a typically dry climate, is negligible: for both the external SRs and the passive DRC-roof, the seasonal occurrence of condensation is below 0.03% of the total operational time. In Rome, which experiences higher ambient humidity, the condensation effect is slightly more pronounced. The rooftop and external SR configurations exhibit a seasonal condensation occurrence of approximately 0.3% of the operational time. The passive DRC-roof configuration displays a higher seasonal condensation rate of 1.5%, with the peak value reaching 4.3% in June.

Condensation can pose a critical challenge for DRC surfaces, as the presence of water can degrade their optical properties, thereby reducing radiative performance [67, 68]. However, for the hydronic DRC-based system analyzed in this study, the impact of condensation remains limited. This is primarily due to the moderate cooling behavior of the system, which typically operates only a few degrees below ambient temperature, and avoids the deeper subcooling associated with fully passive DRC systems. Another factor that can impair performance is soiling, particularly dust accumulation, which can lower the solar reflectivity of DRC surfaces, reduce cooling efficiency, and potentially cause permanent damage, compromising weather resistance [69].

Figure 32: SR and RCM sizing analysis for a single-family building during August (TMY) in Madrid, using commercial DRC emitters, a flow rate of $0.25 \text{ L min}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and the optimal number of pumping hours. a) Comfort index with enhanced pipe insulation. b) Average indoor temperature reduction compared to a passive building (no hydronic cooling and conventional roof) with enhanced pipe insulation. c) Comfort index with enhanced pipe, external sun shading and nighttime ventilation. d) Average indoor temperature reduction compared to a passive building with enhanced pipe insulation, external sun shading and nighttime ventilation.

5.4 Discussion

A DRC-based hydronic cooling system was presented, modeled, and validated using experimental data from a full-scale demonstrator. The system was shown, through dynamic simulations, to achieve full thermal comfort in a real scale residential building under TMY conditions for the cooling season in Madrid (Spain) and Rome (Italy). The validated model was further used to explore the influence of various design parameters, including the number of SRs and RCMs, water flow rate, pumping hours, and emitter material.

The main findings of this study can be summarized as follows:

- (1) The DRC-based hydronic system was compared against a system employing a conventional nighttime emitter (black emitter). Under the tested flow conditions, the use of DRC emitters extended the operation window of the system by 2–3 hours, depending on whether a commercial or ideal broadband DRC was used, and increased the energy removed by the RCMs by up to +6.2% and +10.3 %, respectively.
- (2) A parametric study of different combinations of RCM and SR surface areas during the cooling season in Madrid showed that a comfort index greater than 90% can be achieved with an RCM/SR coverage of 47%/53 %, optimizing the overall system footprint.
- (3) The performance of a hydronic system with external SRs was compared to a rooftop SR configuration, which benefits from the increased roof albedo. Both configurations successfully achieved thermal comfort, with the rooftop SRs offering slightly improved performance. In contrast, a fully passive DRC-roof failed to maintain acceptable indoor comfort levels in both the climates tested.
- (4) The seasonal coefficient of performance of the DRC-based hydronic system reached values as high as 152 in Madrid and 129 in Rome, approximately 40 times higher than typical values reported for conventional mechanical air conditioning systems.
- (5) Enhancing the thermal insulation of the distribution piping and incorporating effective solar shadings for windows significantly reduced the required surface coverage of both RCMs and SRs. In Madrid, a combined coverage as low as 17% (RCM) and 19% (SR) was sufficient to achieve thermal comfort.
- (6) The spectral shape of the spectral emissivity curve of the DRC material can have a relative influence of a few percents on the cooling energy extracted from the building.

These findings underscore the potential of DRC materials to enable energy-efficient and almost completely passive cooling systems for buildings. Such technologies represent a promising avenue for sustainable building design, particularly in mitigating urban heat island effects and city-wide overheating. However, several barriers must be addressed for large-scale adoption. These include the relatively high initial cost of DRC materials, spatial limitations due to surface area demands and competition with other rooftop technologies and performance degradation due to condensation and soiling. Ongoing research and innovation are critical to overcoming these challenges and facilitating the integration of radiative cooling into mainstream building systems. Future studies should also prioritize the development of advanced flow rate control strategies to optimize performance under changing weather conditions, integration of thermal water storage to decouple the hydronic and DRC circuits for improved system flexibility and controllability, and investigation of the screening effects caused by ceiling-mounted radiative modules.

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6 Modeling results - FIW

In Task 2.3 of PaRaMeTriC, FIW (Research Institute for Thermal Insulation Munich) had to estimate the potential of the passive radiative cooling technology on the reduction of energy demand for cooling German residential buildings within the next 30 years by comparison to classical cooling techniques.

This report examines current and projected energy demand for space cooling in Germany and evaluates the potential for energy and CO₂ savings through Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling (PDRC) technologies. Although historically low, air conditioning (AC) penetration in Germany's building stock is expected to rise substantially due to increasing temperatures and more frequent heatwaves.

Germany's building stock is large and heterogeneous, with approximately 19.5 million residential buildings and 41 million households in 2024. Many residential buildings were constructed before 1978, prior to the introduction of national thermal insulation regulations, and only a small fraction falls into high-efficiency energy classes. Non-residential buildings total roughly 21 million, of which only around 2 million are heated and subject to energy performance regulations.

Two complementary approaches are applied to estimate future cooling demand. First, a linear projection based on historical energy consumption and mean annual temperatures indicates that total cooling demand could reach 18.5 TWh by 2050, representing a 70 % increase relative to 2020. Second, a household-based projection calculates residential demand bottom-up from household numbers and typical AC unit consumption, while non-residential demand is derived top-down from total energy consumption. Two scenarios are analysed: Case A, with moderate AC penetration (4 % in 2024 rising to 14 % in 2050) and a 25 % climate-driven demand increase, results in total cooling demand rising from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 13.6 TWh in 2050. whereas Case B adopts the

total energy consumption from the linear projection (18.5 TWh in 2050) and higher AC penetration (8 % in 2024 to 20 % in 2050).

Potential energy and CO₂ savings from PDRC technologies, including envelope-integrated and device-based applications, are estimated as a combined range. Savings in Case A are 110 – 545 GWh and 6100 – 244000 t CO₂, increasing proportionally in Case B to 11 – 741 GWh and 6100–244000 t CO₂. These results demonstrate that PDRC technologies can reduce energy consumption and emissions, particularly under high-demand scenarios.

6.1 Status quo

In order to perform the estimation /projection, the data of the status quo on the climate, building stock, energy consumption and AC unit penetration in Germany is summarized.

Climate and atmospheric window

Data from German weather service (Deutscher Wetterdienst - DWD) show a steady increase of the annual mean air temperature from 7.5 °C in the year 1881 to 9.3 °C in the year 2024. In addition to that, the number of cooling degree days (CDD), divided into summer days (temperature above 25 °C) and hot days (temperature above 30 °C) per year also increased. Following the data trend lines, Germany in 1951 showed 20 summer days, of which 2 were hot days, and now shows 46 summer days, of which 11 were hot days (see Figure 33 and Figure 34). This trend is also not expected to be reduced and will eventually lead to a higher demand in cooling devices / energy in future.

Figure 33: Average annual temperature in Germany from year 1818 to 2023.
Source: Own representation of data from Deutscher Wetterdienst

Figure 34: Number of summer and hot days in Germany from year 1951 to 2023.

Source: Own Representation of data from Deutscher Wetterdienst

The infrared atmospheric window (between 8 – 13 μm wavelength) represents a spectral range in which terrestrial longwave radiation can escape to space with relatively low absorption by atmospheric gases. Although the spectral window is always present in principle, the fraction of outgoing longwave radiation transmitted through it depends strongly on cloud cover and on the amount of water vapor in the atmospheric column. To estimate how often the window can be considered “effectively open” over Germany, two main conditions must be fulfilled:

- Cloud-free sky conditions – Clouds consist of liquid droplets or ice crystals that absorb and emit infrared radiation efficiently across the thermal IR spectrum. Even thin clouds significantly reduce transmission through the 8–13 μm window, effectively blocking direct surface emission. Satellite cloud climatologies (e.g., CLAAS-3, CM SAF) and DWD statistics indicate that truly cloud-free conditions in Germany occur in only about 25–35 % of hours, with seasonal and regional variability (EUMETSAT CM SAF, 2023; DWD, 2024).
- Low precipitable water vapor (PWV) – the total column of atmospheric water vapor controls the degree of transparency under clear-sky conditions. Low PWV (< 10–15 mm) limits absorption by water vapor lines and the water vapor continuum, resulting in effective sky brightness temperatures around 220–230 K and allowing significant radiative loss. Higher PWV (> 20 mm) increases absorption, raises the effective sky temperature toward 270 K, and prevents most surface radiation from escaping directly. The 10–15 mm threshold is based on empirical studies from observational campaigns and radiative transfer modeling, representing the range below which the atmospheric window remains appreciably open (Turner & Mlawer, 2010; Clough & Iacono, 1995)

Satellite-derived datasets (e.g., CLAAS-3 cloud property dataset, CM-SAF, EUMETSAT) and DWD climatological assessments of “fair weather” days indicate that truly cloud-free conditions occur in central Europe in roughly 25–35 % of hours, with substantial regional and seasonal variation. Reanalysis and observational studies for central Europe demonstrate that PWV is lowest in winter (often < 10 mm), intermediate in spring/autumn, and highest in summer (> 20–30 mm). By combining these two constraints the fraction of time in Germany when the infrared window is “effectively open” can be estimated:

- Winter (Dec – Feb): Dry high-pressure episodes allow relatively frequent transmission; the window is effectively open in approximately 25 – 35 % of hours, occasionally higher during persistent cold spells.
- Spring/Autumn (Mar – May, Sep – Nov): More variable cloudiness and moderate PWV lead to approximately 15 – 25 % of hours with open window conditions.
- Summer (Jun – Aug): High humidity and convective cloudiness suppress the window; openness drops to approximately 5 – 15 % of hours.

In Germany, the 8 – 13 μm atmospheric window is always spectrally present, but its practical openness is limited to roughly 15 – 25 % of annual hours, with a strong seasonal cycle. The effective operation of this radiative channel is thus constrained not only by long-term greenhouse gas trends but also by short-term meteorological variability (clouds and PWV).

Building stock

According to the German Energy Agency (dena) Building Report 2024 and based on official statistics from the Federal Statistical Office (Destatis), the total residential building stock in Germany in 2022 amounted to approximately 19.48 million buildings. The dena data provide a breakdown into single-family houses, two-family houses, and multi-family houses:

- Single family houses: ~13.01 million buildings
- Two family houses: ~3.18 million buildings
- Multi family houses (including residential homes): ~3.29 million buildings

This categorisation reflects the typology used in German building statistics, with single-family houses dominating the stock (about two-thirds of all residential buildings).

The dena Building Report 2024 also provides the distribution of the residential building stock by construction period, expressed in percentage shares. For use in this report, these percentages were applied to the total number of 19.48 million buildings to calculate approximate absolute numbers per age class. The calculation assumes that the percentage distribution is representative for the entire stock, as suggested by dena.

- Built before 1945: ~ 24% → approx. 4.68 million buildings
- 1946 – 1977: ~ 36% → approx. 7.01 million buildings
- 1978 – 1983: ~ 8% → approx. 1.56 million buildings
- 1984 – 1994: ~ 11% → approx. 2.14 million buildings
- 1995 – 2001: ~ 8% → approx. 1.56 million buildings
- 2002 – 2008: ~ 5% → approx. 0.97 million buildings
- 2009 – 2013: ~ 3% → approx. 0.58 million buildings
- 2014 and later: ~ 5% → approx. 0.97 million buildings

According to the Federal Statistical Office (Destatis, 2023), the 19.48 million residential buildings contain 41 million households in year 2024. Looking ahead to 2050, household development is expected to follow a compound annual growth rate of 1.2%, in line with medium-range projections for population and housing stock (Destatis, 2023).

While the figure of 19.48 million refers exclusively to residential buildings, there is also a significant stock of non-residential buildings in Germany. According to the Institute for Housing and Environment (IWU), the total number of non-residential buildings amounts to around 21 million. However, only about 2 million of these are heated and thus fall under the scope of the German Building Energy Act (GEG). This distinction is important, as the majority of non-residential structures (such as barns, warehouses, or industrial halls without heating) are not subject to energy performance regulation.

Unlike age and type distributions, the energy performance classification of the building stock is not consistently documented in official national statistics. Instead, available information stems from analyses of energy performance certificates (EPCs). These data are subject to uncertainty, as EPCs are only mandatory in specific circumstances (e.g., sale or rental). Meta-studies by FIW München emphasize that the existing EPC data are incomplete and not fully representative of the national stock.

Nevertheless, secondary analyses of large EPC datasets suggest that only a minority of residential buildings (around 10–15%) fall into the top efficiency classes (A+, A, or B), whereas a significant share (often more than 50% in regional samples) is classified in the lowest categories (F to H).

This overview demonstrates that Germany’s building stock is both large and heterogeneous, with a substantial share of buildings constructed before 1978, i.e., prior to the introduction of the first national thermal insulation regulations and 21 million non-residential buildings of which only a fraction of 2 million are subject to thermal insulation regulations.

Energy consumption for space cooling

Data of the federal ministry of economic affairs and climate action (BMWK) show, that the energy consumption for space cooling has increased from 7.9 TWh in 2008 to 10.9 TWh in 2020. The energy consumption in 2020 is split in 1.2 TWh for residential buildings and 9.7 TWh for non-residential buildings, which include buildings in the industry sector (4.8 TWh), Transport sector (0.6 TWh) and trade / commerce sector (4.3 TWh).

Given the ongoing trend of rising average temperatures and the increasing frequency of heatwaves in Germany, it is expected that both the penetration of cooling technologies and the associated energy demand will continue to grow in the coming decades.

Figure 35: Total energy demand for space cooling in Germany from year 2008 to 2020. Source: Own representation of data from BMWK

Figure 36: Energy demand for space cooling in Germany broken down in sectors from year 2013 to 2020. Source: Own representation of data from BMWK

AC unit penetration

In Germany, the penetration of residential air conditioning (AC) remains comparatively low by international standards. The relatively modest diffusion of AC in Germany is primarily attributable to historical climatic conditions with relatively mild summers and cultural factors favouring passive cooling solutions, such as shading, ventilation, and building design (IEA, 2018). Compared with Southern European countries such as Italy or Spain, where over 90 % of households own AC systems (IEA, 2018; Enerdata, 2021), Germany has

not yet experienced mass adoption. This trajectory positions Germany in a middle range within Europe: higher than Nordic countries (e.g., Sweden and Finland with <2 % penetration; EEA, 2020), but far lower than Mediterranean member states. The German case is thus marked by a delayed but accelerating adoption curve, driven by both climate warming and socioeconomic adaptation.

Study-based estimates suggest that in 2024 approximately 8 % of households own at least one AC unit (European Environment Agency [EEA], 2020; Enerdata, Zebra Monitoring, 2021). A more detailed study by the Öko-Institut (2017) reports a penetration of 3 % in 2015 and a current penetration of 6 % (2025) with projections indicating that up to 14 % of households could adopt AC systems by 2050 under moderate climate warming scenarios.

The European Environment Agency projects that AC penetration in German households could reach 10 – 12 % by 2050 under moderate climate change pathways (EEA, 2021), while the Öko-Institut (2017) model indicates a possible 20 - 25 % penetration, when a high space cooling energy demand growth is assumed.

These projections correspond with the increase in the production of air conditioning units in Germany Between 2019 and 2024 from approximately 181000 units to around 317000 units, representing a rise of more than 75 % (Destatis, 2025; Clean Energy Wire, 2025). Import values followed a similar trajectory, with total imports of air conditioning equipment growing from roughly 640 million € in 2019 to about 957 million € in 2023, before slightly declining to 949 million € in 2024 (Clean Energy Wire, 2025).

Representative surveys indicate that the share of households equipped with air conditioning increased from around 13 % in 2023 to 19 % in 2024 (Verivox, 2024). These developments are consistent with climatic drivers like the increase in summer and hot days per year over the last 2 decades and with the recent summers (2022–2024) ranking among the hottest on record (Umweltbundesamt, 2024; IEA, 2023).

The temporal coincidence of increased heat stress with accelerated growth in production, imports, and household penetration suggests that climate change is a key driver of air conditioning demand in Germany. This indicates the potential for continued market expansion if high-temperature summers persist or intensify.

6.2 Estimation and projection

Based on the data of the status quo, estimations and projections for the years until 2050 are performed. The first attempt shows the alignment of the climate and energy consumption data and a basic estimation on energy consumption with a linear approach.

The second attempt projects the total residential energy consumption based on the known number of private households in combination with typical energy consumption values for AC units and recalculates the non-residential energy consumption from the total energy consumptions for space cooling for the complete building stock. In addition, the projection will be divided in two showcases, of which Case A will demonstrate a moderate AC unit penetration and energy demand growth based on IPCC data and Case B will reflect the development with higher AC unit shares and energy growth rates based on the linear approach from projection attempt 1. Additionally, the second projection until 2050 will also be expanded by factors like household growth rates and device efficiency improvements.

Alignment of climate and energy consumption data

In order to determine a correlation between the data sets for the mean annual temperature and the energy consumption, both data sets are set into relation. With choosing a time period, where both data sets are recorded and putting them into analysis, the linear correlation factor of 0.95 can be derived.

Figure 37: Display of the correlation between the data sets for the annual mean temperature and the total energy consumption for space cooling in Germany. Source: Own representation of data from Deutscher Wetterdienst and BMWK

With following the trend lines of the mean temperature and the energy consumptions, the linear projection of the energy consumption in the following years can be estimated. Starting with 10.9 TWh/a from the last recorded data set from 2020, the energy consumption will increase to 13.8 TWh/a in 2030 and 18.5 TWh/a in 2050. In relation to the baseline value of 2020, the energy consumption for space cooling will increase by 70 %.

Figure 38: Figure 6: Linear projection of the data sets for the annual mean temperature and total energy consumption for space cooling in Germany. Source: Own representation

Projection based on private households

The projection model rests on a set of assumptions that combine demographic, technological, and climatic drivers:

1. Household Stock and Growth: The baseline consists of approximately 41 million households in 2024, in line with the Statistisches Bundesamt (Destatis 2023). A compound annual growth rate of 1.2 % per

year is assumed until 2050, consistent with medium population and housing stock projections (Destatis, 2023).

2. Air Conditioning Penetration:
 - a. Case A: 4 % of households are assumed to own an AC system in 2024 and will rise gradually to 14 % by 2050, reflecting conservative assumptions on AC unit penetration resembling data from Öko Institut and expecting moderate space cooling energy demand growth.
 - b. Case B: assumes a penetration rate of 8 % in households in 2024 following data from EEA (2020) and Enerdata Zebra Monitoring (2021) and will increase up to 20 % in 2050 (Öko Institut, 2017). This reflects higher space cooling demand growth and increasing frequency of extreme heat events (EEA, 2021).
3. Unit-Level Consumption: Each residential AC unit is modeled to consume 0.8 MWh per year, and each non-residential unit 4 MWh per year, consistent with empirical values reported by Fraunhofer ISE (2021) and IEA Cooling Roadmap (2018).
4. Efficiency Improvements. All units are assumed to experience a 1 % per year efficiency gain, reflecting regulatory tightening under EU EcoDesign and technological innovation (IEA, 2021). Efficiency improvement work as a counterpart to the expected demand increase from larger penetration and climate change effects.
5. Climate Change Factor (Total Demand Growth Constraint):
 - a. Case A: The climate effect is modelled as a 25 % increase in cooling degree days and cooling demand by 2050, relative to the 2024 baseline. This is derived from IPCC AR6 projections under the RCP4.5 / SSP2 “stabilization” pathway, which estimates that mean summer temperature increases of approximately +2.0 °C by mid-century in Central Europe will translate into +20–30 % more cooling degree days (Zhou et al., 2019; IPCC AR6 WG1, 2021). A mid-point value of +25 % was chosen as a conservative estimate. This factor alone would increase total German cooling demand from 10.9 TWh in 2024 (BMWK) to ~13.6 TWh in 2050. This parameter method choice is expected as a moderate development for the space cooling energy demand.
 - b. Case B: The total energy consumption for space cooling in 2050 will be set to the projected value of 18.5 TWh/a from the linear projection, which is equivalent to a 70 % increase up to year 2050. This parameter method choice is expected as a more impactful development on the space cooling energy demand.

Due to missing information on the stock of non-residential buildings, the projection will be performed in a self-contained approach. The energy demand for space cooling in residential buildings is derived in bottom up approach based on the household numbers and the typical AC unit energy consumption. The energy consumption for space cooling in non-residential buildings is derived in top-down approach based on the total energy consumption for space cooling (Energy consumption of non-res. = total energy consumption – energy consumption of res.)

For Projection Case A, Parameter 2a) and 5a) will be paired to demonstrate a moderate development in AC unit penetration and energy demand. Parameter 2b) and 5b) will be combined in Case B to reflect a development, where higher AC unit penetrations will be reached in combination with a higher energy demand growth.

The following diagram shows the space cooling energy per year for residential and non-residential buildings of Case A and B.

Figure 39: Projected Residential and non-residential energy demand for space cooling in Germany from year 2024 to 2050 of Case A and B. Source: Own representation

6.3 Discussion

Figure 39 shows the projected residential and non-residential energy demand for space cooling in Germany from 2024 to 2050 for Case A and B. Case A, total cooling demand rises moderately from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 13.6 TWh in 2050. Residential energy demand increases steadily over time, while non-residential demand remains relatively stable and even slightly decreases in certain years. In contrast, Case B exhibits a continuous increase in both residential and non-residential energy demand, rising from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 18.5 TWh in 2050.

By checking the plausibility of the values, it needs to be advised, that this method is self-contained. It starts with a bottom-up calculation based on the number of households and ends with a top to bottom recalculation of the number of AC-Units in non-residential buildings. Therefore, the outcome of this method is mainly related to the start value (private households) and the end value (total energy consumption for space cooling). When comparing the results for the energy consumption of residential and non-residential, it can be seen, that the energy consumption in residential buildings is rising significantly, while the energy consumption in non-residential buildings is stagnating or even decreasing, which is expected to differ from future developments. This outcome is a result of the calculation method with the capped total energy consumption for space cooling.

6.4 Savings from the use of PDRC materials

In order to project the possible savings with PDRC technologies, the projected total energy consumption for space cooling will be used as a baseline. It is also assumed that only a fraction of 10 – 20 % of the buildings will be equipped with PDRC technologies.

With the approach, that PDRC materials will be used directly on the building envelope (roofs, upward faced facades, etc.), it is assumed that in middle European regions, the energy consumption for the conditioning of the building can be reduced by 1 to 5 % (see technical report from NKUA to Task A2.3.2 from Deliverable D3). Alternatively, when PDRC technologies are used in shape of direct cooling devices like heat exchangers, it is assumed, that 10 – 20 % of the energy consumption can be saved (numbers without scientific back up). GHG emissions are calculated with factors following a declining trendline marking 560 g/kWh in 2024, 321 g/kWh in 2030 and 26 g/kWh in 2050 (BMW, 2020).

The following tables show the projected total energy consumptions and assumed energy and correlated GHG emission savings when using PDRC technology.

Case A					
Year	Cooling energy in TWh	PDRC envelope		PDRC heat exchanger	
		Savings in GWh	Savings in t CO ₂	Savings in GWh	Savings in t CO ₂
2024	10.9	11 - 109	6100 - 61000	109 - 436	61000 - 244000
2030	11.5	12 - 115	3700 - 37000	115 - 461	37000 - 148000
2050	13.6	14 - 136	350 - 3500	136 - 545	3500 - 14000

Case B					
Year	Cooling energy in TWh	PDRC envelope		PDRC heat exchanger	
		Savings in GWh	Savings in t CO ₂	Savings in GWh	Savings in t CO ₂
2024	10.9	11 - 109	6100 - 61000	109 - 436	61000 - 244000
2030	12.7	13 - 127	4100 - 41000	127 - 506	41000 - 162000
2050	18.5	19 - 185	480 - 4800	185 - 741	4800 - 19000

In Case A, cooling energy demand increases moderately from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 13.6 TWh in 2050. Correspondingly, energy savings from PDRC interventions also rise over time. The building envelope contributes moderate savings, ranging from 11 – 109 GWh and 6100–61000 t CO₂ in 2024 to 14 – 136 GWh and 350 – 3500 t CO₂ in 2050. In contrast, the heat exchanger offers higher savings from 109 – 436 GWh and 61000 – 244000 t CO₂ in 2024 to 136 – 545 GWh and 3500 – 14000 t CO₂ in 2050. But it should be noted, that the share of savings for heat exchanger is just assumed and not technically proven.

In Case B, projected cooling energy demand is higher, increasing from 10.9 TWh in 2024 to 18.5 TWh in 2050. The estimated savings from PDRC interventions are proportionally greater than in Case A. The building envelope could save between 11 – 109 GWh and 6100 – 61000 t CO₂ in 2024, rising to 19 – 185 GWh and 480 – 4800 t CO₂ by 2050. Heat exchanger savings are higher, ranging from 109 – 436 GWh and 61000 – 244000 t CO₂ in 2024 to 185 – 741 GWh and 4800 – 19000 t CO₂ in 2050, but need to be questioned due to the not proven saving share for the devices.

Overall, both scenarios indicate that PDRC interventions can achieve substantial reductions in energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. The variability in savings highlights the need to consider uncertainty in future projections and the potential range of effectiveness for different PDRC technologies.

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7 Modeling results – CAE

The urban heat island (UHI) effect (Figure 40) causes an increase of the temperature in urban areas, such as larger cities in comparison to the temperature in the urban fringe of 5 K, with peak events of up to 10 K during the summer on warm and clear days. By applying passive radiative cooling surfaces on all rooftops, the urban heat island effect can be reduced by about 1 K.

Figure 40: Illustrative visualization of the urban heat island (UHI) effect.

For evaluation of the impact of large scale use of PRC technique on buildings in urban area, CAE modeled the particular case of an urban Canyon for two locations with an without utilization of PRC material on the buildings envelopes.

7.1 Modeling tool

The thermal simulations of the surface temperatures in urban street canyon as a function of solar irradiation and air temperatures were carried out using Solid Works as FEM software.

7.2 Configurations modeled

The urban canyon configuration modeled is shown in Figure 41. The street surface is asphalt. The modelling were done during the day for clear sky conditions.

Figure 41: Schematic drawing of the canyon with the street (black), the roofs (green) and the walls (grey).

The thermal modellings were done for two locations :

- Denver Colorado (USA) with the conditions: height = 1609 m, date: 21 June, hours: 08:00 to 16:00), clear sky, air flow through the urban canyon = 1 m/s.
- Frankfurt am Main (Germany) with the conditions: height = 112 m, date: 21 June, hours: 08:00 to 16:00), clear sky, air flow through the urban canyon = 1 m/s.

The solar and infrared properties of the materials covering the roofs and the walls of the buildings are given in Table 13.

material	solar absorptance	hemispherical total emittance
typical PRC	0.05	0.90
typical white	0.20	0.90
typical black	0.95	0.90
asphalt	0.90	0.90
best PRC	0.02	0.98

Table 13. Materials covering the roofs and the walls of the buildings

7.3 Results

Denver, Colorado

Figure 42: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs for air temperature set at 20 °C at 15:10 for black and white coatings

Figure 43: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs at 15:10 for air temperature set at 20 °C for typical PRC and typical white coatings

Figure 44: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs at 15:10 for air temperature set at 20 °C for typical PRC and best PRC coatings.

Figure 45: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs at 15:10 for air temperature set at 30 °C or 40 °C for typical PRC and best PRC coatings

Coating on the roofs and walls	air	asphalt	top of south orientated wall		bottom of south orientated wall		roof	
	T_{air} (K)	T_{max} (K)	T_{max} (K)	T_{min} (K)	T_{max} (K)	T_{min} (K)	T_{max} (K)	T_{min} (K)
typical black	293.15	379.47	346.21	323.44	368.01	340.35	351.22	307.31
typical white	293.15	382.54	336.15	308.55	340.81	320.09	317.38	298.59
typical PRC	293.15	383.51	332.83	304.44	337.26	315.06	303.07	295.72
best PRC	293.15	383.79	333.69	302.45	336.51	311.20	306.82	294.39
typical PRC	303.15	385.69	336.89	309.15	339.02	317.51	313.89	303.06
typical PRC	313.15	387.06	339.83	314.47	341.35	322.48	316.11	309.49

Table 14. Calculated temperatures for Denver Colorado USA location

Frankfurt am Main

Figure 46: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs for air temperature set at 20 °C at 15:10 for black and white coatings

Figure 47: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs for air temperature set at 20 °C at 15:10 for typical PRC and best PRC coatings

Figure 48: Resulting temperature distribution of the walls and of the roofs at 15:10 for air temperature set at 20 °C or 40 °C for typical PRC coating

Coating on the roofs and walls	air	asphalt	top of south orientated wall		bottom of south orientated wall		roof	
	T _{air} (K)	T _{max} (K)	T _{max} (K)	T _{min} (K)	T _{max} (K)	T _{min} (K)	T _{max} (K)	T _{min} (K)
typical black	293.15	377.07	357.99	320.41	366.04	341.15	349.97	299.86
typical white	293.15	382.54	337.62	307.33	344.33	324.11	313.13	297.00
typical PRC	293.15	383.79	331.66	301.24	334.84	311.15	308.72	295.07
best PRC	293.15	384.22	330.82	301.88	333.31	311.51	304.44	294.51
typical PRC	313.15	387.52	339.63	313.48	342.20	323.19	321.85	307.73

Table 15. Calculated temperatures for Frankfurt am Main (Germany) location

The solar irradiation onto the walls and the street during the day depends on the respective position of the sun and is visualized in Figure 49.

Figure 49: Solar irradiation onto the walls and the street during the day.

The absorbed power, which depends on the insolation as well as on the solar absorptance, is depicted in Figure 47 along the day in arbitrary units with asphalt as street surface.

Figure 50: Absorbed power in arbitrary units onto the walls and the street during the day.

7.4 Conclusions

Roof temperature is about 20 to 25 K lower with PRC materials (low solar absorptance and high total hemispherical emissivity) than with black coating (high solar absorptance and high total hemispherical emissivity).

Sub-ambient cooling of the roof is visible for the roofs in Figure 45 and Figure 48 with air temperature at 40 °C (313.15 K).

With PRC coating the walls temperatures are above ambient temperature due to radiative and convective heat exchanges with the opposite wall and the street. The south-orientated wall is about 30 K colder with PRC coating than with black coating.

For the configurations treated, the asphalt temperatures obtained with white or PRC coatings on roof and walls are higher, by about 4 to 7 K, than those with typical black coating on roof and walls. This is due to the high solar reflectance on the walls generating high reflectance of incident solar radiation toward asphalt, which absorbs strongly solar radiation. So, in real configuration, if walls are very reflective for solar radiation and the pavement is highly solar absorbing then the temperature of the pavement can become quite high and generates a quite high air temperature at pedestrian height. Furthermore, high reflecting walls can generate a high level of visual discomfort for people in the street.

7.5 Survey of energy consumption for cooling buildings in Europe and the world

In addition to the thermal modelling of an urban canyon, CAE has also collected data about the evolution of cooling power needs for buildings in Europe (Activity A2.3.1 in PaRaMetriC project).

The European building stock can be subdivided between residential and service buildings (Figure 51). The energy consumption of the buildings is depicted in Figure 52 and Figure 53, which give the final energy consumption (FEC) and the useful energy demand (UED). The energy consumption for air conditioning in the different types of buildings is presented in Figure 54 and Figure 55. The energy consumption for space cooling in the world is shown in Figure 56. From Figure 56 it can be seen that not only the total amount of final energy consumption for cooling energy increases but also the share of cooling in the energy consumption of buildings. From 2025 to 2050, the part of cooling energy in energy consumption of buildings is expected to double.

Figure 51: Building stock in Europe 2016

Figure 52: Energy consumption in Europe for space heating and domestic water

Figure 53: Energy consumption in Europe for space cooling

Figure 54: Energy consumption for air conditioning in Europe per type and sector

Figure 55: Energy consumption for air conditioning in Europe for residential and service buildings

Figure 56: Energy consumption for space cooling in the world

8 Conclusions

POLITO, CSIC, and NKUA thermally modeled specific buildings in various locations using real or "realistic" climatic data and calculated the potential energy savings related to the use of passive radiative cooling techniques comparatively to the use of classical air conditioning techniques.

The relative energy savings obtained by POLITO for the case of a single-family dwelling equipped with a compression air cooling system assisted, for subcooling refrigerant, by PDRC panels are about 6% to 10% for a period of three months in hot season (June, July, August).

CSIC thermally modeled, with help from POLITO and CNR-INO, a typical building equipped with a "hydronic cooling system" and calculated the potential reduction of energy demand if PDRC technique is used. The main finding is: the cooling energy is relatively increased by about +6.2% and +10.3% by comparison to a "hydronic cooling system" where the cooling effect is exploited only during night. The seasonal coefficient of performance of a PDRC-based hydronic system can be approximately 40 times higher than typical values for compression air conditioning systems (electrical power is only for water circulation).

NKUA thermally modeled four different buildings (three single family houses and a six-story residential block) in four different locations in south of EU. The main outcomes of the study are: the use of PRC yield strong reductions of cooling needs for the detached single or two-story houses (-23.8% to -75.2%); the relative reductions of cooling needs are very high (-51.7% and -75.2%) for the two houses with less insulated roofs; for the six-story residential block, the relative cooling energy gain due to the use of PRC is of -8.7% for the top floor. For the whole year, the substantial reduction in cooling can be largely offset by increased heating consumption (less solar gains during heating season). PDRC techniques are very effective for reducing cooling needs for less thermal insulated buildings in hot and dry regions.

For the evaluation of the potential impact of large-scale deployment of PRC coating on heat-island effect, NKUA modeled an urban area at two locations in Greece. The air temperatures and the temperatures of the building envelopes were calculated for the buildings roofs coated with a PRC material and for the buildings covered with the usual materials. The main conclusion is that the cooling effect on air temperature at pedestrian height is moderate (about 0.6 K) even if the mean reflected solar radiation is substantially increased (170%) by the use of PRC material. The modellings of impacts of PRC techniques at large scale would require more detailed modellings of the indirect heat transfers of heat from the buildings to air in streets when buildings absorb a high proportion of solar radiation.

CAE modeled the particular case of an "urban canyon" when the buildings roofs and walls are not treated or are treated with a PRC material. The air temperature was set at a fixed value, and the temperatures of the surfaces were calculated. With a PRC technique the roofs can be 20 to 25 °C colder than with a high solar absorption. With PRC coating the walls remain at a temperature above ambient temperature but are colder by 25 to 30 °C than with a high absorption. A drawback of PRC coating applied on the walls is the higher temperature of the asphalt surface in the street due to high solar absorptance of asphalt and higher reflection

of solar irradiation toward asphalt by the walls. CAE showed also that the world share of energy for cooling buildings should double from 2025 to 2050.

FIW estimated the potential for energy and CO₂ savings through Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling (PDRC) technologies. For that FIW made a detailed survey of the building stock in Germany. FIW evaluated that the energy demand for cooling could increase by 25% to 70% from 2020 to 2050 in Germany depending on the scenario. Potential related energy and CO₂ savings from PDRC technologies, including envelope-integrated and device-based applications, are estimated from 11 to 545 GWh and 6100 – 244000 t CO₂ if AC penetration is moderate and from 11 to 741 GWh and 6100–244000 t CO₂ if AC penetration is higher. These results demonstrate that PDRC technologies can participate in the reduction of the energy consumption and emissions, particularly under high-demand scenarios.

Annex – POLITO technical reports

Determination of the potential cooling power attainable by PRC materials

A steady-state and transient numerical model was developed to quantify the cooling potential of various passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials. This model has been employed to characterize the thermal behavior of these materials and to conduct a sensitivity analysis assessing their cooling performance under varying atmospheric conditions. The model numerically solves the surface thermal energy balance equation for a PRC emitter with a surface A_p :

$$Q_{\text{rad}} - Q_{\text{atm}} - Q_{\text{sun}} - Q_{\text{conv}} = C_p \frac{dT_p}{dt} \quad (1)$$

The variable T_p denotes the temperature of the emitter, while C_p represents its total thermal capacity. The term C_p represents the transient thermal storage component, which vanishes under steady-state conditions.

The net cooling flux is defined as: $Q_{\text{net}} = Q_{\text{rad}} - Q_{\text{atm}} - Q_{\text{sun}} - Q_{\text{conv}} \quad (2)$

According to this sign convention, a positive net flux ($Q_{\text{net}} > 0$) indicates that the surface is experiencing net cooling, whereas a negative net flux ($Q_{\text{net}} < 0$) corresponds to net heating of the surface.

Q_{rad} is the radiative power emitted by the panel toward the sky. It can be expressed as:

$$Q_{\text{rad}} = \pi A_p \int_0^\infty \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \varepsilon_{\text{prc}}(\lambda, \theta) I_b(\lambda, T_p) \sin(2\theta) d\theta d\lambda \quad (3)$$

ε_{prc} is the emissivity of the PRC material, function of the wavelength λ and the view angle θ . Dependence on the azimuthal angle is typically neglected in engineering applications due to its minimal impact. I_b is the spectral radiance of a blackbody, function of wavelength and surface temperature and calculated as by Planck's law:

$$I_b(\lambda, T) = \frac{2hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{hc/(\lambda k_B T)} - 1} \quad (4)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum, h is the Planck constant and k_B is the Boltzmann constant. The emitter is assumed to be perfectly horizontal, with an unobstructed view of the sky, such that no surrounding objects interfere with its radiative exchange.

Q_{atm} is the radiative power absorbed from the atmosphere. It is calculated by solving the following equation:

$$Q_{\text{atm}} = A_p \int_0^\infty \varepsilon_{\text{prc}}(\lambda) Z(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (5)$$

$Z(\lambda)$ is the spectral-dependent hemispherical downward longwave atmospheric radiation at the surface. The term is computed using the Longwave Rapid Radiative Transfer Model (RRTM_LW). The downward longwave atmospheric radiation is resolved over 16 spectral bands. This model allows to take into account also the presence of clouds, which influence the effective temperature of the sky.

In case the clear sky conditions, the following equation can be used to evaluate Q_{atm} :

$$Q_{\text{atm}} = \pi A_p \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \varepsilon_{\text{prc}}(\lambda, \theta) \varepsilon_{\text{atm}}(\lambda) I_b(\lambda, T_{\text{amb}}) \sin(2\theta) d\theta d\lambda \quad (6)$$

Here, the atmosphere is considered as a body characterized by a spectral-dependent emissivity ε_{atm} , emitting at the ambient temperature T_{amb} . ε_{atm} can be expressed as a function of the precipitable water vapor amount w through this formula:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{atm}}(\lambda) = 1 - \exp[a_0(\lambda) + a_1(\lambda)w + a_2(\lambda)w^2 + a_3(\lambda)w^3] \quad (7)$$

where a_0 , a_1 , a_2 and a_3 are fitting coefficients from Ref. [1].

Q_{sun} is radiative power absorbed from the sun (equal to zero in nighttime conditions). It can be calculated as:

$$Q_{\text{sun}} = A_p G \frac{\int_0^{\infty} \varepsilon_{\text{prc}}(\lambda) I_{\text{AM}1.5}(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_0^{\infty} I_{\text{AM}1.5}(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (8)$$

where G is the total solar irradiance at the surface and $I_{\text{AM}1.5}$ is the solar spectral radiance at air mass 1.5 (conventionally used for solar technologies).

Q_{conv} represents the convective losses/gains of the DRC surface. The emitter is assumed to be perfectly insulated on its lateral and rear surfaces, thereby eliminating conductive and convective heat losses from those boundaries. As a result, the only non-radiative heat exchange occurs at the exposed top surface, driven by natural convection or wind-induced advection. The convective heat transfer is given by:

$$Q_{\text{non-rad}} = A_p h_p (T_{\text{amb}} - T_p) \quad (9)$$

h_p is the convective heat transfer coefficient between the emitter and the air, estimated using the correlation with wind velocity from Ref. [2].

Figure 1 presents the net cooling flux as a function of the temperature difference between the emitter and the ambient environment for two PRC materials evaluated during the PaRaMetric project: *SpaceCool* and *3M*. These materials are compared with two idealized references: a spectral selective (SS) emitter and a broadband (BB) emitter. The SS emitter is modeled with an emissivity of unity within the atmospheric transparency window (8–13 μm) and zero outside this range. In contrast, the BB emitter is characterized by an emissivity of zero between 0–4 μm and unity elsewhere. All performance curves are generated under clear-sky conditions using the model in Ref. [1], assuming a convective heat transfer coefficient $h_p = 10 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, $T_{\text{amb}} = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and a relative humidity (RH) of 50%. The shaded regions around each curve indicate the variability associated with RH values ranging from 20% to 80%, reflecting realistic operating conditions.

Under radiative equilibrium conditions ($Q_{\text{net}} = 0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$), the *SpaceCool* material achieves temperature reductions of 0.72°C and 6.41°C below ambient during daytime and nighttime, respectively. In comparison, the *3M* material exhibits temperature drops of 1.09°C and 6.35°C under the same conditions. For reference, the ideal SS and BB emitters attain temperature reductions of 7.67°C and 6.62°C , respectively, during both daytime and nighttime, (due to their assumed 100% solar reflectivity).

For $T_p = T_{\text{amb}}$, the *SpaceCool* PRC material exhibits net cooling power fluxes of 10.9 W m^{-2} during the day and 96.8 W m^{-2} at night. The *3M* PRC material, under the same conditions, demonstrates cooling fluxes of 16.7 W m^{-2} during the day and 96.7 W m^{-2} at night.

Figure 1. Daytime (left) and nighttime (right) net cooling flux vs. temperature for different PRC materials. The curves are evaluated in clear sky conditions, at $h_p = 10 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$, $T_{\text{amb}} = 25^\circ\text{C}$ and for rh between 20% and 80% (shaded area).

Figure 2 presents the net cooling flux as a function of the temperature difference between the emitter and the ambient of the previously mentioned real and ideal materials, with a varying heat transfer coefficient h_p between $0 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ (convective effects completely suppressed) and $20 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$, corresponding to moderate wind velocities.

Complete suppression of convective heat losses provides insight into the minimum equilibrium temperatures achievable by PRC materials. Under representative environmental conditions— $T_{\text{amb}} = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $RH = 50\%$ and clear sky,—SpaceCool attains minimum temperatures of approximately -1.1°C during daytime and -19.1°C at nighttime. Under the same conditions, the 3M material reaches -2.0°C and -18.4°C during day and night, respectively. For comparison, the ideal selective surface achieves a minimum temperature of -43.9°C .

Figure 2. Daytime (left) and nighttime (right) net cooling flux vs. temperature for different PRC materials. The curves are evaluated in clear sky conditions, at $T_{\text{amb}} = 25^\circ\text{C}$, $RH = 50\%$ and for h_p between 0 and $20 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ (shaded area).

Figure 3 presents the results of a combined sensitivity analysis with respect to both the temperature difference between the emitter and the ambient, and the incident solar irradiance. This analysis enables the construction of an operational map for the PRC materials under clear sky conditions, assuming a fixed convective heat transfer coefficient ($h_p = 10 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$). Additionally, it facilitates the identification of the locus of points where $Q_{\text{net}} = 0$, which can be approximated by a linear function. To the right of this line, the emitter operates in a net cooling regime.

For the SpaceCool PRC, the zero net cooling condition is described by the linear equation $y = 158.5x + 957$, while for the 3M PRC it is given by $y = 171.6x + 1020$.

Figure 3. Net cooling flux vs. temperature and solar irradiance for the following emitters: ideal SS (top left), ideal BB (top right), SpaceCool (bottom left), 3M (bottom right). The curves are evaluated in clear sky conditions, at $T_{amb} = 25^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 50\%$ and for $h_p = 10 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$.

Lumped-element dynamic model of an air source heat pump

Following the development of the PRC emitter model, it was employed to simulate the thermal behavior of PRC-coated flat radiative panels. These panels are designed to enhance the performance of a conventional air-cooled vapor compression heat pump used for space cooling. To enable cooling during daytime operation, as the heat pump is active throughout the day, and the panels are equipped with a daytime radiative cooling (DRC) material.

Specifically, the PRC-coated panels are integrated into an external closed-loop circuit and are used to cool a heat transfer fluid, consisting of a water and ethylene glycol (EG) mixture. The cooled fluid is then circulated through an auxiliary heat exchanger, referred to as the ‘subcooler’, which is installed downstream the air-cooled condenser of the heat pump. This configuration provides an additional cooling contribution to the refrigerant, thereby improving the seasonal energy efficiency rating (SEER) of the heat pump and reducing overall electricity consumption. A schematic representation of the DRC-enhanced heat pump system is shown in **Figure 4**. The model is fully developed in MATLAB-Simscape environment.

The heat pump under investigation is an air-to-water vapor compression refrigeration system (VCRS) employing R1234yf, a refrigerant characterized by a low global warming potential. The VCRS is modeled as a multi-component thermal system comprising six primary elements: evaporator, compressor, condenser, expansion valve, subcooler, and refrigerant accumulator.

Figure 4. DRC-enhanced heat pump, plant schematic

The evaporator is modeled as a shell-and-tube counter-flow exchanger, with R1234yf flowing through the tube side and a water–EG solution circulating within the shell side. The air-cooled condenser is modeled as a cross-flow finned-tube exchanger, wherein refrigerant flows inside circular tubes arranged in an in-line array, while ambient humid air flows orthogonally across the finned surfaces and in parallel with the flat plates.

The compressor is a volumetric (positive-displacement) unit operating at a nominal mass throughput and rotational speed of 1000 rpm. Its operation is regulated via a binary thermostat-based control mechanism, whereas the refrigerant mass flow rate through the expansion device is modulated by dynamically adjusting the orifice area to achieve the design superheat at the evaporator outlet. While the evaporator superheat remains fixed throughout operation, subcooling at the condenser outlet varies dynamically, governed by the operation of the DRC-panels array.

The subcooler is modeled as a counter-current tube-in-tube heat exchanger, with the water–EG solution circulating through the annular (shell-side) region and R1234yf flowing within the inner tube. The geometric and thermal sizing of the heat exchanger is based on the target design subcooling, which constitutes a critical parameter in the overall thermal performance.

Operational constraints and thermodynamic boundary conditions for the refrigerant cycle are delineated in **Table 1** and **2**, respectively. The condenser saturation temperature is set to 50 °C to ensure functional stability during peak ambient thermal conditions. The evaporator is sized to deliver a cooling capacity of 8 kW.

Table 1. Heat pump thermodynamic cycle constraints

State	Pressure (bar)	Temperature (°C)
1	3.61	6
2	13.02	55.1
3	13.02	48
4	3.61	6

Table 2. Heat pump thermodynamic cycle design conditions

Parameter	
Refrigerant flow rate (kg/s)	0.079
Evaporator temperature (°C)	4
Evaporator superheating (°C)	2
Condenser temperature (°C)	50
Condenser superheating (°C)	2
Compressor isentropic efficiency	75%

The DRC subsystem is hydraulically coupled to the VCRS condenser via a closed-loop water–EG circuit, which comprises a circulation pump, an expansion reservoir, and the already described subcooler. The DRC panel assembly is modeled as a flat-plate radiator consisting of an aluminum plate thermally bonded to a copper serpentine embedded beneath the surface. Each unit panel features an effective radiative area of 1 m²; several panels are connected in series to achieve the required surface area. A spectrally selective DRC coating is applied to the upper surface of the aluminum plate, exposed to the atmospheric dome.

The thermal energy dissipated by the VCRS condenser is transferred to the DRC serpentine via convective exchange with the circulating water–EG mixture. Conductive transfer from the serpentine to the aluminum plate takes place, enabling radiative rejection to the sky. Circulation within the DRC subsystem takes place only when the VCRS compressor is running.

At the emitter interface, the thermal model solves a modified formulation of Equation 1, incorporating an additional term accounting for the convective heat transfer delivered by the water–EG mixture, that is cooled down while it flows inside the embedded serpentine. This term is a function of the effective thermal resistance between the water–EG stream and the emitter surface, which is in turn governed by the material properties, flow regime, and geometrical configuration of the serpentine-emitter system.

A comprehensive description of the geometrical specifications for all components, along with detailed system parameters and control strategies, is provided in the Annex. Performance results evaluating the operation of the DRC-integrated heat pump across various operational and environmental conditions are presented in the section referring to the subtask A2.3.2.

References

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- [2] D Zhao, A Aili, Y Zhai, J Lu, D Kidd, G Tan, X Yin, and R Yang. Sub-ambient cooling of water: toward real-world applications of daytime radiative cooling. *joule* 3, 111–123, 2019.

PRC-enhanced air source heat pump

The numerical model developed for the DRC-enhanced air-source heat pump, as outlined in Task A2.1.5, has been integrated with a dynamic simulation model of a residential building cooled via water-source fan coil units (FCUs). This coupling enables the quantitative assessment of energy savings generated by the implementation of PRC materials. The complete schematic of the plant configuration is presented in the section corresponding to Task A2.1.5.

The modeled building is a single-family dwelling consisting of two conditioned floors and an unconditioned attic, with a total usable floor area of 174 m². The building envelope components—including walls, floors, roofs, slabs, windows, and doors—are modeled as thermal masses, while the indoor air is modeled as moist air. The thermal insulation properties of the various building elements were sourced from the TABULA database [1] and correspond to construction practices for buildings erected between 1991 and 2005. **Table 1** presents the global heat transfer coefficients of the principal envelope components, while **Table 2** details the corresponding material stratigraphy. The optical properties of both opaque and transparent surfaces exposed to the external environment—such as solar absorptivity, thermal emissivity, and g-factor—are summarized in **Table 3**.

Table 1. Global heat transfer coefficient U of the constituents of the building

	Roof	Ext. walls	Upper slab	Lower slab	Windows	Doors
U (Wm ⁻² K ⁻¹)	2.20	0.59	0.69	0.77	2.80	1.70

Table 2. Stratigraphy of the building components

	Materials	Area (m ²)
Ext. walls	Hollow bricks, Rock wool, Air gap, Solid bricks	223.3
Roof	Hollow bricks, Rock wool, Tiles	96.4
Lower slab	Tiles, Rock wool, Concrete	96.4
Upper slab	Hollow bricks, Rock wool, Concrete	96.4
East window	Glass with multi-Argon gaps (80%), Pine wood frame (20%)	6.52
South window	Glass with multi-Argon gaps (80%), Pine wood frame (20%)	8.69
West window	Glass with multi-Argon gaps (80%), Pine wood frame (20%)	6.52
North window	Glass with multi-Argon gaps (80%), Pine wood frame (20%)	0
Door	Pine wood	2.40

Table 3. Optical properties of the building components

	Ext. walls	Roof	Door	Windows
Solar absorptivity	0.3	0.7	0.3	-
Thermal emissivity	0.9	0.8	0.9	-
G-factor	-	-	-	0.75

The thermal loads incorporated in the model of the building include heat transfer through external surfaces, solar gains via both absorption by opaque elements and transmission through glazing, internal heat generation, and ventilation-related heat exchange resulting from both air infiltration and mechanical ventilation. For simplification, thermal re-radiation effects are considered only for the roof surface, while re-radiation from vertical external walls is neglected. The building facades are oriented along the four cardinal directions, and the roof is assumed to be flat and horizontal. The DRC-coated panels are installed horizontally on the roof; the changes in roof albedo due to their presence are explicitly accounted for in the simulation. A comprehensive description of the thermal and optical properties of the building, material stratigraphy, and the governing equations implemented in the model is provided in the Annex.

The building is conditioned by means of fan coil units (FCUs). The evaporator of the heat pump is hydraulically connected to the indoor FCUs through a closed-loop circuit containing a water–ethylene glycol (EG) mixture. This circuit also includes a circulation pump and a small buffer tank. Each indoor FCU is modeled as a cross-flow tube-fin heat exchanger, with the water–EG mixture flowing through the tube side and moist air passing over the finned surface. The airflow is oriented perpendicularly to the bank of circular tubes, which are arranged in an inline configuration, and flows parallel to the finned plates. Further geometric and modeling details of the FCUs are provided in the Annex.

The full system, comprising the residential building and the DRC-enhanced heat pump, is simulated over a representative cooling season in the northern hemisphere, spanning from June to August. Meteorological input data are sourced from the ERA5 Reanalysis dataset for the year 2023. Simulations are conducted for four distinct locations: Las Vegas (USA), Riyadh (Saudi Arabia), Madrid (Spain), and Turin (Italy), representing various Köppen–Geiger (KG) climate classifications. Las Vegas and Riyadh are characterized by a hot desert climate, with minimal annual precipitation and elevated summer temperatures. Madrid exhibits a hot-summer Mediterranean climate with dry summers, while Turin experiences a warm temperate oceanic climate with moderate summer temperatures. **Table 4** reports the average values of key atmospheric variables for each location during the simulation period.

Table 4. Information on the locations tested; air temperature, relative humidity, cloud cover, downwelling longwave atmospheric radiation (DWLWAR) and wind velocity are reported as average seasonal values

City	Latitude	Longitude	KG Zone	Air Temp. (°C)	Rel. Humidity (%)	Cloud Cover (%)	DWLWAR (W/m ²)	Wind Velocity (m/s)
Riyadh	24.7	46.7	BWh	36.7	11.4	13.1	384	3.0
Las Vegas	36.2	-115.1	BWh	29.2	23.7	25.9	357	2.4
Madrid	40.4	-3.7	Csa	26.4	39.1	25.0	355	2.5
Turin	45.0	7.7	Cfa	23.7	58.6	46.2	362	2.1

The total power consumption of the plant is defined as the sum of the electrical power consumed by the heat pump compressor (P_{comp}), the fans of the condenser ($P_{fan,cond}$) and the FCUs ($P_{fan,FCU}$), the circulation pump of the FCUs circuit ($P_{pump,FCU}$), and the circulation pump of the DRC-panel circuit ($P_{pump,DRC}$). The integration of these contributions over the entire simulation period (T) yields the total electric energy consumption (E):

$$E = \int_0^T (P(t)_{comp} + P(t)_{fan,FCU} + P(t)_{fan,cond} + P(t)_{pump,FCU} + P(t)_{pump,DRC}) dt \quad (1)$$

The total electric energy consumption is compared with that of a conventional heat pump without the DRC enhancement (E^0). The plant configuration remains identical, except for the absence of the DRC-driven subcooler. This comparison enables the evaluation of both the absolute (ΔE) and relative ($\Delta E_{\%}$) energy savings:

$$\Delta E = E^0 - E \quad \Delta E_{\%} = \frac{E^0 - E}{E^0} \quad (2)$$

Analogously, it is also possible to quantify the relative variation in the heat pump running time ($\Delta U_{\%}$) and in the seasonal energy efficiency ratio ($\Delta SEER_{\%}$):

$$\Delta U_{\%} = \frac{U^0 - U}{U^0} \quad \Delta SEER_{\%} = \frac{SEER - SEER^0}{SEER^0} \quad (3)$$

The SEER is defined as:

$$SEER = \frac{\int_0^T P(t)_{evap} dt}{\int_0^T P(t)_{comp} dt} \quad (4)$$

where P_{evap} is the thermal power removed by the evaporator from the indoor environment.

A parametric analysis of key operational variables within the plant is subsequently carried out. A dynamic simulation is conducted over the entire time domain to assess the impact of the following parameters on overall system performance: the surface area of the DRC-panels (A_p), the size of the subcooler (expressed as the design temperature drop $\Delta T_{D,sc}$), and the flow rate in the panels (expressed in specific terms G_p/A_p). **Figure 1** presents the results of this parametric analysis, conducted under the climatic conditions of Las Vegas, using an emitter characterized by the following properties: solar reflectivity of 99%, emissivity in the atmospheric window (8–13 μm) of 99%, and emissivity beyond this range (>13 μm) of 35%. Hereafter, this material is referred to as spectral selective + far-IR (SSFIR).

Figure 1. Sensitivity analysis on panel net and radiative flux and subcooler temperature drop (a-c), specific and absolute electric energy savings (d-f) and seasonal EER increase, heat pump uptime decrease and relative energy savings (g-i). (a,d,g) The effect of panel array surface at $G_p/A_p=1.5$ L/min/m² and $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 8^\circ\text{C}$. (b,e,h) The effect of subcooler size at $G_p/A_p=1.5$ L/min/m² and $A_p = 8$ m². (c,f,i) The effect of panel specific flow rate at $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 8^\circ\text{C}$ and $A_p = 8$ m². These results are for a DRC system located in Las Vegas simulated with meteorological data for June-August. The shaded areas quantify the variability of the variables (as a standard deviation).

Figures 1a-c report the impact of panel surface area, subcooler size, and flow rate on the subcooler temperature drop (ΔT_{sc}), net cooling flux (Q_{net}), and radiative cooling flux (Q_{rad}). The latter term is defined as the sum of the radiative contributions, which include panel radiative power, solar flux absorbed by the panel, and the atmospheric flux absorbed. The temperature drop in the subcooler increases with both panel area and subcooler size, reaching a saturation point. However, the flow rate has a negligible effect, with the temperature drop remaining largely unaffected. The net flux increases with both subcooler size and flow rate, as the mean temperature of the emitter rises, thereby enhancing the radiative flux. On the contrary, Q_{net} decreases with the increase in DRC panel area. This occurs because, for a fixed subcooler size (i.e., the same amount of heat is extracted from the refrigerant fluid), the heat is distributed over a larger surface, causing the emitter to operate at lower temperatures, which results in lower net and radiative fluxes.

Figures 1d-g illustrate the effects on absolute and specific energy savings. Energy savings increase in a manner similar to the temperature drop in the subcooler with both panel area and subcooler size. The maximum energy saving is achieved for a surface area between 8-10 m², beyond which the increase in pumping energy associated with a larger panel area is not sufficiently compensated by the reduction in the electrical energy consumption of the plant. For flow rate, maximum energy savings are reached at 1.5 L/min/m². Specific energy savings, normalized by emitter area, decrease as panel area increases, due to the saturation effect on energy savings with respect to area.

Figures 1g-i demonstrate that the relative energy savings follow a similar trend to absolute savings. The increase in the heat pump SEER and the decrease in heat pump uptime both increase monotonically with panel surface area and subcooler size. Again, the specific flow rate has minimal impact on these parameters.

Figure 2 presents the results of the sensitivity analysis conducted on the emitter material. The model was executed under identical operational and meteorological conditions, with variations only in the DRC emitter. The materials evaluated include the previously described SSFIR, an ideal broadband (BB) emitter, an ideal spectral selective (SS) emitter, and two commercial materials—SpaceCool (denoted as "Commercial 1", C1) and 3M (denoted as "Commercial 2", C2).

Figure 2. Effect of 5 different DRC emissivity profiles (SSFIR, BB, SS, C1 and C2) on (a) electric absolute and relative energy savings and (b) radiative and net flux. These results are for a DRC system with $A_p = 10 \text{ m}^2$, $G_p/A_p = 1.5 \text{ L/min/m}^2$, $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 12 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, located in Las Vegas and simulated with meteorological data for June-August.

As shown in Figure 2a, the BB emitter exhibits the highest relative energy savings (8.5 %), followed closely by the ideal SS (8.3 %) and SSFIR (8.2 %). The commercial materials demonstrate lower performance, with energy savings of 7.0 % for SpaceCool and 7.2 % for 3M, corresponding to a relative reduction in performance of -18.0% and -16.0% , respectively, when compared to the ideal BB emitter.

Figure 2b illustrates the average net and radiative fluxes (represented by empty markers) and their variability (represented by error bars) for each material. As expected, the BB emitter achieves the highest fluxes. Although the ideal SS emitter produces slightly lower fluxes, it exhibits reduced variability, indicating more stable operation. This stability is attributed to its diminished sensitivity to atmospheric thermal radiation. In contrast, the commercial materials display substantially lower radiative and net fluxes compared to the BB emitter. This reduced performance is primarily attributed to their solar reflectance, measured at 90.5 % for SpaceCool and 91.1 % for 3M, which increases their susceptibility to solar load.

Figure 3a presents the electric energy savings achieved by integrating a DRC-driven subcooler into a heat pump across four geographical locations and two building energy classes, under identical operating conditions. Riyadh, with the highest average ambient temperature, exhibited the greatest seasonal savings: 46.1 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC} for the Standard building and 38.0 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC} for the Modern building. Subsequent values were observed in Las Vegas: 37.5 and 27.7 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}, Madrid: 20.1 and 12.5 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}, and Turin: 9.6 and 7.5 kWh_{el} m⁻²_{DRC}. The superior performance of the system in Riyadh and Las Vegas is attributed to both high cooling demand and favorable radiative cooling conditions (low humidity and cloud cover). Conversely, Turin showed the lowest savings due to low cooling demand and unfavorable summer climate, with high humidity and cloudiness.

Figure 3. Analysis of DRC panels performance by geographical location. (a) Electric energy savings at $A_p = 8 \text{ m}^2$, $G_p/A_p = 1.5 \text{ L/min/m}^2$ and $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 12^\circ\text{C}$ for Modern and Standard building. (b) Electric energy savings at $A_p = 8 \text{ m}^2$, $G_p/A_p = 1.5 \text{ L/min/m}^2$ and $\Delta T_{D,sc} = 12^\circ\text{C}$ for the Standard building across June–August.

The relative energy savings for Standard buildings were -9.9% (Madrid), -8.1% (Las Vegas), -6.9% (Turin) and -6.3% (Riyadh). Notably, the locations achieving the highest relative energy savings were not those achieving the highest absolute savings, suggesting that relative energy reduction, commonly used as a performance metric, may not fully capture the benefits of radiative cooling. Absolute savings—normalized by DRC surface area or conditioned floor area—constitute a more representative measure of performance.

Figure 3b illustrates the monthly distribution of energy savings (June–August). In Riyadh, savings remained nearly constant, while Las Vegas showed a pronounced peak in July. In Madrid and Turin, the highest savings coincided with the hottest months—July and August, respectively. These results indicate that absolute energy savings of heat pump–assisted VCRS systems are primarily governed by cooling demand (heat pump runtime), with meteorological conditions exerting a secondary influence. It should be noted that the reported savings are based on 2023 meteorological data and do not represent general performance; for broader applicability, Typical Meteorological Year data should be employed.

References

[1] Tobias Loga, Britta Stein, and Nikolaus Diefenbach. Tabula building typologies in 20 European countries—making energy-related features of residential building stocks comparable. *Energy and Buildings*, 132:4–12, 2016.